

Elsevier Editorial System(tm) for Ecological Modelling
Manuscript Draft

Manuscript Number: ECOMOD-13-34R1

Title: LARVAHS: Predicting clam larval dispersal and recruitment using habitat suitability-based particle tracking model

Article Type: Research Paper

Keywords: Ruditapes decussatus, Ruditapes philippinarum, larvae, particle-tracking model, habitat suitability, ENFA, swimming behavior, recruitment, connectivity.

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Abstract: We herein explore the potential larval dispersal and recruitment patterns of *Ruditapes decussatus* and *Ruditapes philippinarum* clams, influenced by larval behavior and hydrodynamics, by means of a particle-tracking model coupled to a hydrodynamic model. The main contribution of this study is that a habitat suitability-based (ENFA, Environmental Niche Factor Analysis) settlement-recruitment submodel was incorporated into the larval dispersal model to simulate settlement behavior and post-settlement mortality. For this purpose, a specific study was carried out in the Bay of Santander (Northern Spain), a well-mixed shallow water estuary where shellfishery of both species is carried out. The model was fed with observed winds, freshwater flows and astronomical tides to obtain predictions during the clams spawning period. Dispersion of larvae from 7 spawning zones was tracked, subjected to three-dimensional advection, vertical turbulent diffusion and imposed vertical migration behavior parameterized from existing literature. Three simulation periods (Spring, Summer and Autumn) and 2 initial releases (spring / neap tide) were combined in 6 different modeling scenarios. The LARVAHS model proved to be a powerful approach to estimating recruitment success, highlighting the role of habitat suitability, larval swimming behavior, planktonic duration, season (i.e. predominating winds) and spawning ground location on recruitment success together with the effect of the tidal phase at spawning. Moreover, it has proven to be a valuable tool for determining major spawning and nursery grounds and to explore the connectivity between them, having important implications for restoration strategies and shellfisheries as well as aquaculture management.

Response to Reviewers: See "Detailed responses to reviewers" after the letter to editor (below, 3rd page).

Dear Editor,

We should like to thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised version of our manuscript entitled “*LARVAHS: Predicting clam larval dispersal and recruitment using habitat suitability-based particle tracking model*”. We hope you will consider this new version suitable for possible publication in Ecological Modelling.

Following recommendations made by the anonymous reviewers we have fully revised our paper and we now specifically address key issues related with the model sensitivity to habitat suitability and larval behavior. For this purpose, we conduct for all scenarios new simulations using LARVAHS model without incorporating (1) the behavior submodel and (2) the habitat suitability-based recruitment submodel and we compared results obtained with those obtained using the original LARVAHS model.

We also decided to shorten the manuscript, give more cohesion to the paper, and being less emphatic presenting results as new and innovative. Moreover, we removed non informative figures and move important supplementary information (Tables, Figures) to the main manuscript.

Please find below the comments of reviewers (in Black) and our responses (in Blue), including the list of changes made in the manuscript.

We wish to thank Editor and the anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments.

We hope that this new version of the manuscript will be acceptable for publication in Ecological Modelling.

Sincerely yours,

Dr. Gorka Bidegain

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Detailed Responses to Reviewers

- **Reviewer 1:**

General comments

The manuscript examined, through a numerical modelling approach, the larval dispersal and recruitment patterns of two clams species: the native *Ruditapes decussatus* and introduced *Ruditapes philippinarum* in the bay of Santander (Spain).

The originality of this study relied on the use of a habitat suitability-base settlement-recruitment sub-model, obtained by ENFA (Environmental Niche Factor Analysis), which was incorporated into a 3D larval tracking model with imposed vertical migration.

Three seasonal winds (spring, summer, autumn), and two initial releases (neap/spring tide) were tested. Recruitment patterns and connectivity measurement were then compared and the most important spawning sites and nursery grounds were identified accordingly.

Despite a low absolute concordance between simulated and observed data, the seasonal and inter-specific variations appeared well reproduced, mainly for *R. philippinarum*.

This study gives new insights on the population dynamics of the two clams species in the bay of Santander, and develops a valuable modelling strategy to go a step forward in closing the larval loop, by understanding the recruitment success or post settlement mortality.

The manuscript is well-written and structured, and develops an original modelling strategy.

My main concerns are about the ENFA, and the habitats treatment, which appeared to me not sufficiently detailed in the present work. I understand that there is a manuscript submitted on this subject, but some information are lacking in the present work to properly understand the method and interpret the results (e.g. post-settlement mortality, see specific comments). I thus suggest to give a short description of the ENFA in the introduction section and to improve the method section accordingly.

Differences between the two species in the validation step are not well examined and might be more deeply described and discussed.

The distinction between the PLD and the behavior appears ambiguous and could be more explicit, by clearly state what is related to the PLD and what is related to the specific vertical displacement.

The "larval dynamic" section in the results does not appear to me very informative and might be removed.

I also noted an error in the results of recruitment (Fig. 7A, see specific comments).

I thus recommend that the article should be accepted for publishing in Ecological Modelling, with minor revisions, according to the following comments.

[These general comments of reviewer 1 are commented again, point by point, in the specific](#)

comments section. In order to not be repetitive in our responses, we responded these comments below in the specific comments section.

Specific comments

Title

The title clearly described the article. ✓

Keywords

They clearly describe the scope of the manuscript. ✓

Abstract

The abstract well reflects the content of the article. ✓

Highlights

The highlights give a good summary of the work. ✓

Introduction

The introduction is well structured and provides a pertinent summary of the context through relevant references.

My only concern in the introduction is about the ENFA and HSI, which are not introduced. Since this is the core of this study, a short description of this analysis would be interesting, for example before the last paragraph.

We agree with this comment and as a result we have decided to better describe ENFA analysis and HSI. We achieved this aim by adding or rewriting several paragraphs dealing with these issues in the introduction (see response in this section, below) and in the model description (see responses in the “material and methods” section, within “settlement-recruitment sub-model” sub-section):

In the Introduction section we add the following paragraph dealing with ENFA and HSI, lines 126-132:

“...the model includes a larval behavior submodel and a settlement-recruitment submodel based on the habitat suitability resulting from Ecological Niche Factor Analysis (ENFA), a niche-based predictive habitat suitability modelling technique for presence-only data based on multivariate ordination. ENFA compares distributions of eco-geographical variables between the locations where the species is present and the whole area, extracting the range of environmental conditions of the locations that the species inhabits, or the niche width and habitat suitability maps based on a habitat suitability index (HSI) (Hirzel, 2001; Hirzel et al., 2002).”

P7 - L30 replace "mayor" by "major"

Corrected. Line 140.

Material and methods

My main concern on this section is also about the ENFA, which is not enough described. Even if the manuscript contains numerous Figures, a map giving the HS index could be informative. In addition, a short description of the ENFA design is needed to properly understand the HSI. Finally, the link between the survival probability of settled particle and the HSI has to be detailed.

We agree with this comment (which is also commented by reviewer 2) and we decided to better describe the habitat suitability-based recruitment submodel (see below response in the “material and methods” section, within “settlement-recruitment sub-model” sub-section) together with the description of ENFA in the introduction section (see above).

Moreover, as it was suggested by reviewer 1 we include a map giving the HS index for both species (see below the new Figure 2a,b and caption in bold).

Figure 2 – Habitat suitability (HS) maps obtained from Bidegain et al. (2013) for *R. decussatus* (a) and *R. philippinarum* (b) in the Bay of Santander, classified into 4 HS index (HSI) classes using GIS techniques: unsuitable ($HSI < 25$), barely suitable ($25 \leq HSI < 50$), moderately suitable ($50 \leq HSI \leq 75$), highly suitable ($HSI > 75$). Spawning zones for *R. decussatus* (c) and *R. philippinarum* (d) considered in the simulations, delimited by areas with habitat suitability index values greater than 75 (i.e. highly suitable areas). Density of adult clams (> 20 mm) found by Bidegain et al. (2012) in each zone following the methodology of Juanes et al. (2012) is presented in brackets. A different color is given to each spawning ground which

also represents the larvae coming from each of them in Figure 6.

Section 2.1; "The bathymetric grid [...] 244 x 298 cells". I suggest moving this sentence into the "model description" section.

Corrected. We agree with this comment and we decided to delete the sentence "The bathymetric grid [...] 244 x 298 cells" in section 2.1 and move into the model description section 2.2 as follows in lines 181-182:

...“The grid used in the model is defined by 244 x 298 cells, each measuring 51x51 m.”

Figure 1; I suggest improving this Figure: authors should give an overall map (e.g. north coast of Spain), to be able to locate the Santander bay. A scale is needed and a north arrow also. Names of the rivers could also be added. A title and units should be added on the depth scale.

Corrected. We add an overall map of the coastline of Spain and France, the scale, the north arrow and the name of the main river (see Figure 1A). We also decided to include in the same figure (following the suggestions of reviewer 2) the hydrodynamic patterns: we include tidal-river mean annual currents (Figure 2B) considering tidal force is similar for all seasons and river outputs were low in general ($< 2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) and not significantly different between seasons (Bidegain et al., 2013) and wind current seasonal patterns (Figures 2C-E).

Figure 1 - Study area for the model: Bay of Santander estuary and adjacent waters located in the northern coast of Spain (Gulf of Biscay). Bathymetry (m) data of the modeled area are presented. Tidal-river annual mean currents (ms^{-1}) (a, b, c) and wind currents (d, e, f) for Spring, Summer and Autumn scenarios.

Figure 1 Caption: replace "fro" by "for" in the first line.

Corrected. Line 1107.

Section 2.2.1; details on the square cells of the model could be provided here.

Corrected. We agree to move this sentence "The bathymetric grid [...] 244 x 298 cells" into the model description section, but we move it into the general section of the model description (section 2.2) as commented above better than into "2.2.1 Hydrodynamic model" subsection, considering that the larval dispersal model, developed coupling a particle tracking and a hydrodynamic model (and not only the hydrodynamic model) contains this grid.

Section 2.2.2;

Disappearance sub-model; the parameter (k) in the equation is not explicitly described. I understand that the larval mortality rate was unique (98%). Thus the time (t) in the equation corresponds to the PLD. This has to be explained because it means that the timing of settlement and the time of searching for a suitable habitat do not modify the mortality rate.

We agree with this comment and consequently we have decided to better describe the disappearance sub-model. We achieved this aim by adding or rewriting several paragraphs dealing with these issues in the sub-model section (see lines 255-268) as follows:

"Disappearance sub-model

The disappearance sub-model associates first-order decay to each simulated particle in order to reflect the egg and larval mortality induced by natural causes (predation, starvation, etc.) (Morgan, 1995). We assumed egg duration of 1 day (Table 1) and a natural egg mortality of 99% for both species, considering that the percentage of fertilized eggs in low population densities is 1% (Levitan, 1995). During the planktonic larval duration (Table 1), we assumed a natural larval mortality of 98% for both species, adapting results obtained by several authors (e.g. Carriker, 1961; Chícharo and Chícharo, 2001b; Zhang and Yan 2006).

$$dN/dt = -kN$$

where N is the number of eggs released, t is the specific life cycle duration (see Table 1) in seconds and k is the considered egg or larval mortality rate (s⁻¹) to obtain the assumed natural mortality percentages."

Settlement-recruitment sub-model; this section could include a short description of the ENFA so as to properly understand what determine the habitat-suitability. How is exactly calculated the habitat suitability index (HSI)? Why authors have chosen HSI = 25 as a threshold for recruitment?

How the survival probability was exactly determined by the HSI value?

I suggest improving this section in order to give more information to the reader on the settlement-recruitment sub-model.

We agree with this comment and as a result we have decided to better describe the settlement-recruitment sub-model by adding or rewriting several paragraphs dealing with determination of HS in the settlement-recruitment sub-model subsection (in lines 270-298) as follows by

rewriting the whole paragraph of this subsection:

“Settlement-recruitment sub-model

We used a habitat-suitability (HS) raster-based grid to determine if a pediveliger-stage larvae encountered a suitable habitat to settle and recruit. Each cell of the grid had a HS index (HSI) which ranged from 0 to 100, with higher values being more suitable for recruitment and zero being completely unsuitable. This grid was obtained from the ecological niche factor analysis (ENFA) conducted successfully by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) for each of the studied species in the Bay of Santander obtaining reasonably good model validation results (see Figure 2a). Different topographic (depth), physical (salinity, current velocity and sediment characteristics such as percentage of sand, gravel and silt) and chemical environmental variables (organic matter content in sediment), assumed as meaningful to the ecology and distribution of these species (e.g. Laing and Child, 1996; Vincenzi et al., 2006, Cannas, 2010) were considered, together with presence data to perform this analysis. The integration of habitat suitability grids in the model grid was automatic since the extent of the study area and the cell size used were identical.

The minimum HSI value considered for recruitment to occur was 25, assuming a HSI value from 0 to 25 to be an unsuitable habitat for recruitment (see Figure 2a,b). For every internal time step (30 s), each pediveliger-stage particle was tested to determine if it was at the sea-bottom. When it was at the bottom, the sub-model checked if the HSI on this cell was greater than 25 and in that case, the particle settled, or stopped moving. When the HSI was lower than 25, the particle continued swimming. Finally, if the particle did not encounter a cell of $HSI > 25$ at the end of the pediveliger-stage, the particle dies.

Once a given particle settled in a cell, the HSI value of this cell was assumed as the survival probability of the particle. To perform the larval recruitment, the model generated a random number between 0 and 100. If this random number was lower than the survival probability of the particle (the HSI), the settled particle survived and it was successfully recruited. On the contrary, if the random number was greater than the survival probability of the particle, the settled particle died.”

Section 2.3.1; what can explain the choice of $HSI = 75$ to define the "highly suitable" spawning area? Why is it different to the $HSI = 25$ for the nursery grounds?

On the one hand, the choice of HSI (Habitat Suitability Index) values greater than 75 was used to define the limits of highly suitable spawning areas assuming that these areas should have a higher density and reproductive efficiency of adults since they are determined by an Ecological Niche Factor Analysis conducted by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) in the Bay of Santander.

We add a sentence (see in bold) in the following paragraph in section 2.3.1 (Line 305) in order to better explain this choice:

“Initial conditions for the simulations were defined for the major spawning areas in the Bay of Santander. Spawning areas were considered those defined as highly suitable ($HSI > 75$) for both species by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) **using ENFA (see Figures 2a,b), assuming a higher density and reproductive efficiency of adults in these areas.** Thus, using this criterion we determined 6 spawning grounds for *R. decussatus* and 7 for *R. philippinaurum* (Figures 2c,d).”

On the other hand, the choice of minimum HSI values of 25 for recruitment was used to analyze which are the major spawning areas regarding the final recruitment of clams in whole the Bay associated to larvae released from a given and previously defined spawning ground (i.e. areas with $HSI > 75$). The choice of a $HSI > 25$ to determine the total recruitment in the Bay, was done assuming HSI from 0 to 25 as an unsuitable habitat for recruitment (see **settlement-recruitment submodel response and figure xxx**). Moreover, the highly suitable nursery grounds were also defined by the choice of a $HSI > 75$. This identical criterion to delimitate highly suitable spawning and nursery grounds was assumed to be ecologically suitable and facilitates the interpretation of results regarding major spawning areas, recruitment densities and connectivity between grounds, since lower HSI values to determine grounds lead to their overlapping. Trials with lower HSI values gave us problems in this regard.

This issue is described in section 2.5.3 in the following rewritten paragraph (lines 397-406):

“Delimitation of nursery grounds by cells $HSI > 25$ (i.e. where recruitment occurs in the model) was not viable if we were to analyze recruitment spatial patterns, since most of the nursery grounds overlapped using this criterion (see Figures 2a,b). Therefore, we decided to consider the nursery grounds as being identical to the spawning grounds (i.e. highly suitable areas, $HSI > 75$) in order to have them clearly separated from each other, facilitating the analysis and interpretation of results regarding the determination of major nursery grounds and/or connectivity between grounds. To determine major nursery grounds, recruitment density was calculated in each ground by adding together larvae coming from different spawning grounds at different tidal and seasonal scenarios and dividing the number of individuals by the nursery ground area (= spawning ground area).”

Figure 2 Caption; data in brackets (density) must be mentioned in the caption and the unit of the density must be précised.

We agree with this comment and as a result we moved the sentence regarding this issue from text to Figure 2 caption (lines 1116-1118) mentioning the significance of data in brackets, as follows (see lines in bold):

Figure 2 – Habitat suitability (HS) maps obtained from Bidegain et al. (2013) for *R. decussatus* (a) and *R. philippinarum* (b) in the Bay of Santander, classified into 4 HS index (HSI) classes using GIS techniques: unsuitable ($HSI < 25$), barely suitable ($25 \leq HSI < 50$), moderately suitable ($50 \leq HSI \leq 75$), highly suitable ($HSI > 75$). Spawning zones for *R. decussatus* (c) and *R. philippinarum* (d) considered in the simulations, delimited by areas with habitat suitability index values greater than 75 (i.e. highly suitable areas). **Density of adult clams (>20 mm) found by Bidegain et al. (2012) in each zone following the methodology of Juanes et al. (2012) is presented in brackets.** A different color is given to each spawning ground which also represents the larvae coming from each of them in Figure 6.

Section 2.4; P16-L17 replace "smaller" by "larger" since authors try to avoid counting early (thus larger) recruiters.

We agree with reviewer 1 that this paragraph regarding the measurements of early recruiters is not clear enough. We considered early recruiters for each season the individuals sieved with a 1mm mesh size sieve (i.e. larger than 1 mm) but smaller than 3 mm for *R. decussatus* and 5 mm for *R. philippinarum* trying to avoid counting early recruiters of the previous spawning season.

In order to better describe the methodology followed to select individuals considered as

recruiters we add “but” in the sentence (**see in bold**) in the following paragraph (Line 362):

“All samples were passed through a 1 mm sieve and clam lengths were measured to the nearest 0.1 mm. Individuals larger than 1 mm **but** smaller than 3 mm for *R. decussatus* and 5 mm for *R. philippinarum* were considered as early recruiters. This selection criterion was based on differential growth patterns described for these clam species (Arnal and Fernández-Pato, 1977, 1978; Spencer et al., 1991; Solidoro et al., 2000; Chessa et al., 2005) as well as the desire to avoid counting early recruiters of the previous spawning season.”

Section 2.5.2; P17-L28 replace "analysis" by "analysis".

Corrected. Line 389.

We replace “multifactorial analysis” by “multifactorial ANOVA”

Section 2.5.3; The treatment of the nursery grounds seems ambiguous. Why the spawning ground were identified with $HSI > 75$ and settlement location by $HSI > 25$? What can explain this difference? I think it related to the ENFA design and to this end, a short explanation of the concepts should improve the methods understanding.

We understand that this issue is not clear enough in this section and we decided to rewrite the section. We hope that these corrections together with the response to section 2.3.1 will facilitate the understanding differences between delimitation of spawning and nursery grounds and determination of most important ones.

The section was rewritten as follows (lines 391-406):

“2.5.3. Determination of major spawning and nursery grounds

We calculated, for the eggs released in each spawning ground (i.e. $HSI > 75$), the proportion of larvae recruited in the whole Bay (i.e. $HSI > 25$) and defined as the most successful spawning grounds those from where, after larval release and dispersal, the highest total recruitments or percentages were obtained.

Delimitation of nursery grounds by cells $HSI > 25$ (i.e. where recruitment occurs in the model) was not viable if we were to analyze recruitment spatial patterns, since most of the nursery grounds overlapped using this criterion (see Figures 2a,b). Therefore, we decided to consider the nursery grounds as being identical to the spawning grounds (i.e. highly suitable areas, $HSI > 75$) in order to have them clearly separated from each other, facilitating the analysis and interpretation of results regarding the determination of major nursery grounds and/or connectivity between grounds. To determine major nursery grounds, recruitment density was calculated in each ground by adding together larvae coming from different spawning grounds at different tidal and seasonal scenarios and dividing the number of individuals by the nursery ground area (= spawning ground area).”

Result

Section 3.1; the difference between the 2 species appeared significant since the recruitment density predicted for *R. decussatus* is largely more overestimated than the recruitment density

predicted for *R. philippinarum*. This has to be noticed and discussed. I wonder how the authors can explain this difference.

Consequently, the relation between observed and predicted recruitment appears highly supported by the results obtained for *R. philippinarum*.

Does it suggest that the habitat suitability model for *R. decussatus* would be less efficient than for *R. philippinarum*?

Or does it mean that there is another factor (e.g. behavior), which could be not properly treated.

We noticed that the Figure 4a and the caption were not clear enough in the original manuscript regarding visualization of results and differentiation between sub-figures (we did not add labels for the four sub-figures included in Figure 4A). This fact could have hindered the interpretation of specific results.

Moreover, Figure 4b, representing relationship between observed and predicted data, was not very informative considering the data shown are not differentiated by species. Therefore, firstly, we decided to remove the Figure 4b and considering the large number of Figures in the manuscript the correlation analysis results for each species were presented in text.

Secondly, the comparison between observed and predicted recruitment is now shown in Figure 3 (before in Figure 4A). It shows that the model is reasonable suitable in its ability to forecast the seasonal variability of recruitment. We add the labels “a,b,c,d,” to name the sub-figures of the Figure 3 (before in Figure 4A) in order to facilitate visualization of the results for each species and zone. Moreover, attending to both reviewers comments regarding the effect of larval behavior and habitat suitability on recruitment we also evaluated two variations of the model: the LARVAHS model without incorporating (1) the behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and the habitat suitability based recruitment submodel. In consequence, we redraw the Figure 4, now Figure 3, and rewrite the caption and the section “3.1. Model evaluation” in order to better explain the model evaluation results, the role of the LARVAHS submodels on recruitment estimations and correlations between observed and predicted recruitment.

“3.1. LARVAHS model evaluation (lines 417-438)”

The LARVAHS model estimations were evaluated in two zones (Raos and Elechas) and for the three studied seasons (Spring, Summer, Autumn) revealing that the predicted recruitment density values were lower than the mean observed values in general, for both species and all seasons (see black circles in Figure 3), except in the summer scenario in Raos. The generalized underestimation of the LARVAHS model was not significantly different between species considering that when underestimation occurred it was $3.62 (\pm 1.47) (\pm \text{SD})$ individuals/m² for *R. decussatus* (Figures 3a,b) and $3.28 (\pm 2.09)$ individuals/m² for *R. philippinarum* (Figures 3c,d). Figure 3 shows that the seasonal variability in recruitment patterns was detected by the LARVAHS model, obtaining significant correlation values between observed and predicted recruitment density for *R. decussatus* (Spearman’s $R=0.89$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 4.1$, $p=0.0$) and *R. philippinarum* (Spearman’s $R=0.94$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 5.6$, $p=0.005$) which involves a good qualitative fit of the model to the in situ measured data.

However, seasonal variability in recruitment was not detected by the two variations of the LARVAHS model and the correlation values obtained between predictions and observed data were not significant, neither for the NO BEHAVIOR model (*R. philippinarum*, $R=0.07$, $n=6$, t

(n-2) = 0.14, p=0.89; *R. philippinarum*, R=0.70, n=6, t (n-2) = 1.94, p=0.12), nor for the NO HS model (*R. philippinarum*, R=0.46, n=6, t (n-2) = 1.05, p=0.35; *R. philippinarum*, R=0.430, n=6, t (n-2) = 0.95, p=0.40). Moreover, the NO BEHAVIOR model results underestimated the observed data more significantly than the LARVAHS model in all cases for both species, and using the NO HS model the overestimation was highly appreciable (Figure 3).”

“Figure 3 – Observed (white quadrates) and predicted recruitment (individuals/m2) obtained with LARVAHS model (black circles), NO BEHAVIOR model (gray triangles) and NO HS model (black crosses) are presented. Results are presented for Spring, Summer and Autumn season scenarios, for *R. decussatus* (A, B) and *R. philippinarum* (C, D) in Elechas and Raos sites respectively Error bars for observed data represent the standard error.”

Thus, in this new figure, we present recruitment values for *R. decussatus* in sub-figures above (3A, Elechas site; 3B, Raos site) and for *R. philippinarum* in sub-figures below (3C, Elechas site; 3D, Raos site). With this labeling, it is easier to visualize that differences between predicted and observed values are not significant between species.

With these results in hand we cannot conclude that the predicted recruitment for any of the

species is more overestimated or underestimated than the predicted for the other species. Therefore, we cannot discuss about differences between specific predictions. However, we can say that the model can detect qualitatively the seasonal recruitment variability which we cannot say regarding the two variations of the model.

Previously in methods section these variations of the model were presented as follows in lines 342-348:

“ 2.4. LARVAHS model evaluation

A preliminary evaluation of the LARVAHS model to predict recruitment of clams was conducted in two nursery grounds (Elechas and Raos) by comparing predictions with observed data. Moreover, two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of larval behavior and habitat suitability in recruitment: (1) a LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) a LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model)...”

Section 3.4; how can we judge that the vertical behavior is "correctly simulated" since there is no information on the observed behavior? The result can be described, but a validation of this model is needed to be able to judge the validity of the model.

We appreciate and agree with the comment by the reviewer regarding the validation of the behavior submodel, but unfortunately we do not have data on the observed behavior. In this work, we adapted previous studies results on behavior of this genus.

At the same time, we wish to point out that in Section 3.4 Model Evaluation (now section 3.1) we evaluate the model results comparing predicted recruitment versus observed recruitment. As the reviewer suggests we cannot judge the validity of the model in terms of behavior and, therefore, we avoided to use the word “validation” and we named this section “model evaluation” since it is an evaluation or description of the results obtained by the model and variations of the model compared with observed data.

In any case, we agree that readers should be made aware of this issue and so we have changed the following paragraph in the **discussion section** and included some lines regarding model validation (lines 715-723).

“The model predicted seasonal recruitment variability reasonably well although, like other similar models, it cannot reproduce the orders of magnitude variability since it does not include many important biological processes (e.g. specific larvae behavior, gamete fertilization success, larval mortality and growth, etc.). Thus, future analyses should be conducted upon these results by assessing the potential contribution of these parameters. Moreover, it is essential to validate the results obtained using the model through comparison with new observed data such as larvae concentration at different levels of the water column and early recruiters (< 250 microns) density.”

Figure 6 & related paragraph; I am not really convince that this part of the results properly represents the larval dynamics since the recruitment patterns include the mortality and HSI. The connectivity results appear to me more valuable, coupled with the ANOVA results, to identify the patterns of larval dynamics and forcing factors.

I thus suggest to remove this part (which is also not discussed) and to support the connectivity

pattern results with the video 2. The section 3.4 could, thus, include only the result of the vertical behavior model with video 1 and Figure S1.

We have read again this section and agree with this comment and others related about this section by reviewer 2 and we consider that this section is definitely improvable.

As a result we have decided to better organize and describe results section 3 in general to a better understanding and organization of this section. Moreover, we move videos 1 and 2 to supplementary information and Figure S1(larval behavior) and Table S1 form supplementary information to this section (following reviewer 2 suggestions) in order to have the key results and information available in print version (see Figure 4 and Table 2 in the reviewed manuscript). Although, reviewer 1 comments are regarding subsection 3.4, we decided to present here all corrections and changes done due to the entire results section and an index of the new organization by new subsections.

Thus, in the original manuscript the results section was organized as follows by 7 subsections:

- 3.1. LARVASH model evaluation
- 3.2. Hydrodynamic variability
- 3.3. Simulation results data
- 3.4. Larval dynamics
- 3.5. Influential factors on recruitment success
- 3.6. Major spawning and nursery grounds
- 3.7. Connectivity between spawning and nursery grounds

In the reviewed manuscript we only include 4 sections as follow:

- 3.1. LARVASH model evaluation
- 3.2. Simulation results data
- 3.3. Larval dynamics
- 3.4. Influential factors on recruitment and connectivity between grounds
 - Season and winds*
 - Spawning zones*
 - Major nursery grounds and connectivity with spawning grounds*

This new organization of results' subsections include this changes:

- We include in the “3.1. Model evaluation” section results (in text and Figure 3) of two LARVAHS model variations (see response to section 3.1, above).
- We eliminate subsection 3.2. “Hydrodynamic variability” following reviewer 2 suggestions regarding the too detailed description of hydrodynamic variability and the inclusion of hydrodynamic patters figures in Figure 1.

Thus, we describe and present hydrodynamic patterns more synthesized in Figure 1 (see response in section 2.1 regarding Figure 1) and section 2.3.3 (in bold) as follows in lines 326-340:

“2.3.3. Simulation scenarios and environmental conditions

Three spawning seasons were tested within the identified spawning period for both species (April-November, Rodríguez-MoscOSO et al., 1992; Rodríguez-MoscOSO and Arnaiz, 1998; Urrutia et al., 1999; Ojea et al., 2005): Spring, Summer and Autumn 2010. In each season two egg releases were tested: 15/04 and 25/04 (Spring), 12/08 and 20/08 (Summer), and 09/10 and 16/10 (Autumn) in 2010. The first date of release in each season coincided with neap tide and the second one with spring tide. **Tidal-river and wind currents during simulation periods are presented in Figure 1. The seawater circulation pattern due to tidal and river forcing is presented as mean annual currents (Figure 1b) considering that the tidal force is similar for all seasons and river outputs were low in general (< 2 m³/s) and not significantly different between seasons (Bidegain et al., 2013). Regarding winds, each season was mainly characterized by a predominating wind: SW winds in Spring, NE winds in Summer and W winds in Autumn, resulting in northward/offshore (Figure 1c), southward/inshore (Figure 1d) and eastward wind currents (Figure 1e) respectively.** Thus, 6 scenarios were tested from each spawning zone and species, corresponding to different tidal phases and seasons.”

- We have rewritten section “3.3. Simulation results data”, now in section 3.2, since we incorporated results of the two variations of the model NO BEHAVIOR and NO HS together with LARVAHS results (see table 2 in the reviewed manuscript). The section 3.2. is presented as follows in the reviewed manuscript in lines 442-464:

“3.2. Simulation results data and model sensitivity

Results of the 78 runs, 36 runs for *R. decussatus* and 42 runs for *R. philippinarum* are presented in Table 2 for the LARVAHS model and the two described variations of this model: the LARVAHS model without the behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and the LARVAHS model without the habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). For each spawning zone the particles released were different, according to the zone extension and the density of adults clams. Thus, for *R. decussatus* Cubas the Outer ground, with ~ 800000 x 10⁵ eggs released, was the most “egg productive” spawning zone, followed by Astillero and Pedreña with ~ 188000 x 10⁵ and ~ 164000 x 10⁵ eggs released, respectively. Additionally, the Pedreña spawning zone, with 963000 x 10⁵ eggs released was the most productive zone for *R. philippinarum*, followed by Elechas with ~ 333000 x 10⁵ eggs released. “

Run	Season	Tide	Zone of release	Released (n)		Recruited LARVAHS (%)		Recruited NO BEHAVIOR (%)		Recruited NO HS (%)	
				<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R.phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R.phil.</i>	<i>R.dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>
1-37	Spring	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.036	0.144	0.009	0.027	0.461	1.027
2-38	Spring	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.009	0.011	0.001	0.002	0.282	0.639
3-39	Spring	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.062	0.036	0.019	0.000	0.690	0.804
4-40	Spring	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.215	0.460
5-41	Spring	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.005	0.015	0.006	0.030	0.191	0.628
6-42	Spring	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.004	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.234	0.384
43	Spring	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.808	–	0.410	–	1.587
7-44	Spring	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.014	0.089	0.007	0.051	0.337	0.818
8-45	Spring	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.203	0.353
9-46	Spring	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.030	0.006	0.008	0.000	0.439	0.722
10-47	Spring	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.115	0.242
11-48	Spring	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.056	0.297	0.018	0.390	0.187	0.717
12-49	Spring	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.011	0.052	0.009	0.035	0.200	0.524
50	Spring	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.676	–	0.290	–	1.514
13-51	Summer	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.222	0.687	0.029	0.350	1.480	1.623
14-52	Summer	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.034	0.200	0.026	0.230	0.994	1.225
15-53	Summer	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.089	0.064	0.021	0.074	1.219	1.319
16-54	Summer	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.024	0.051	0.021	0.220	0.914	0.909
17-55	Summer	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.015	0.536	0.766
18-56	Summer	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.009	0.052	0.013	0.080	0.722	0.908
57	Summer	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.115	–	0.360	–	1.718
19-58	Summer	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.084	0.260	0.070	0.210	0.973	1.202
20-59	Summer	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.011	0.021	0.022	0.097	0.898	0.920
21-60	Summer	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.121	0.032	0.038	0.068	1.393	1.231
22-61	Summer	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.013	0.016	0.020	0.070	0.934	0.890
23-62	Summer	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.020	0.015	0.002	0.019	0.964	0.951
24-63	Summer	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.052	0.002	0.052	0.951	0.978
64	Summer	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.006	–	0.090	–	1.746
25-65	Autumn	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.104	0.447	0.013	0.260	0.934	1.256
26-66	Autumn	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.016	0.041	0.007	0.290	0.352	0.589
27-67	Autumn	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.018	0.038	0.062	0.110	0.634	0.844
28-68	Autumn	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.308	0.643
29-69	Autumn	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.000	0.007	0.001	0.001	0.392	0.699
30-70	Autumn	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.035	0.009	0.068	0.378	0.681
71	Autumn	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.149	–	0.310	–	1.769
31-72	Autumn	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.021	0.101	0.007	0.069	0.358	0.817
32-73	Autumn	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.248	0.412
33-74	Autumn	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.038	0.040	0.010	0.002	0.809	0.790
34-75	Autumn	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.006	0.001	0.001	0.288	0.553
35-76	Autumn	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.006	0.007	0.002	0.001	0.292	0.810
36-77	Autumn	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.007	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.396	0.699
78	Autumn	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.824	–	0.190	–	1.722

“Table 2 – Predicted recruitment scores (%) for simulated *R. decussatus* (*R. dec*) and *R. philippinarum* (*R. phil.*) eggs released (= released particles x 10⁵) from each spawning zone (Astillero, Elechas, Raos, Pedreña, Cubas Outer, Cubas Inner, Solía-Tijero) in each seasonal (spring, summer and autumn) and tidal amplitude (spring or neap tides) scenario, for a total of 36 runs for *R. decussatus* (1-36, left digit in column 1) and 42 for *R. philippinarum* (37-78, right digit in column 1). Results computed by (1) LARVAHS model, (2) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS) are presented.”

“The recruitment percentages were very low for the LARVAHS model and also for the two variations of the model, due mainly to high natural mortality rates and low retention of larvae within the Bay, or to settlement in unsuitable zones. Recruitment success was significantly higher for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus* (see Table 3) for LARVAHS (df=76, t=-3.38, p=0.001) and also for the two model variations (No Behavior, df= 76, t=-2.45, p=0.01; No HS, df= 76, t=-4.48, p=0.0003). The analysis of the variance of recruitment success between models showed significant differences between all of the models for both species, with the significantly highest recruitment for the NO HS model and the lowest recruitment percentages for the NO BEHAVIOR model (Table 3).”

Species	Recruitment succes (%)			ANOVA test				
	LARVAHS	NO BEHAVIOR	NO HS	df	SS	MS	F	p
<i>R. decussatus</i>	0.03 ±0.01 A	0.01 ±0.002 B	0.58 ±0.06 C	2	75.8	37.9	122.3	***
<i>R. philippinarum</i>	0.20 ±0.05 A	0.11 ±0.02 B	0.93 ±0.06 C	2.0	70.0	35.0	37.7	***

“**Table 3** – Recruitment success (% , Mean ± SE) for *R. decussatus* (n= 36 simulations) and *R. philippinarum* (n=42) obtained using (i) the LARVAHS model, which incorporates larval behavior and habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, (ii) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and) (iii)LARVAHS model with no Habitat Suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). Results of the analysis of variance between recruitment obtained using different models are presented at right (*= p<0.05; **= p<0.001; ***= p <0.0001). Tukey HSD – test results are presented by letters (A, B, C) placed after each model mean. If any two means have at least one letter in common, they are not significantly different.”

- Regarding section 3.4. Larval dynamics we are agree with reviewer 1 and hence we decided to describe in this section only the vertical dynamics (moving Figure S1 from supplementary information into this section as Figure 4) and briefly describing spatial dynamics and citing video S2 in supplementary information to visualize this spatial dynamic. We have rewritten this section as follows in lines 468-479, now in section 3.3:

“3.3. Larval dynamics

The assumed vertical behavior of *R. decussatus* and *R. philippinarum* larvae adapted from literature (see Table 1) was correctly simulated (see Figure 4 and Video S1, supplementary information). During the trocophore phase, we found all larvae at the surface (Figure 4a) while D and early Umbo-stage larvae were found at surface to intermediate depths (Figure 4b). Late Umbo and early Pediveliger-stage larvae were found uniformly distributed at all depths (Figure 4c), while late Pediveliger larvae were observed close to the bottom (Figure 4d). Regarding spatial dynamics, Video S2 (see supplementary information) helps to visualize larval pool movements and shows the plume of larvae alternatively flushed in and out of the Bay with the tidal currents, and a differentiated retention of larvae depending on

the zone of spawning. Nevertheless, final recruitment spatial patterns occurring after larval dispersal and influential factors are described in later sections.”

“Figure 4 – *R. decussatus* larval dynamics regarding vertical behavior are in time sequential figures: (A) Day 1 (B) Day 5, (C) Day 15 and (D) Day 18. Dots on left subfigures and lines on right subfigures of each sequential figures represent the particle-tracking of two randomly selected larvae.”

We decided to rewrite, synthesized and organize 3.5, 3.6, 3.7 subsections of the original manuscript in a unique section (3.4) in order to link results about influential factors, connectivity and spawning and nursery zones, as follows in lines 484-558:

“3.4. Influential factors on recruitment and connectivity between grounds

Recruitment data (i.e., the percentage of the total released eggs successfully recruited) were first log-transformed to achieve normality and homogeneity of variance. The factorial ANOVA results presented in Table 4 shows that season (i.e. predominating winds) and the location of the spawning zone have significant effects on the final recruitment success of both clam species. The location of spawning zone contributed more importantly to the overall variance. Additionally, the tidal phase (spring or neap) at the spawning moment had no significant effect on the recruitment of either of the two species. However, the interaction between these two factors had a significant effect for *R. decussatus* (Table 4) and a tidal effect on connection patterns between spawning and nursery grounds can be appreciated (Figure 8). “

Recruitment succes (%)						
<i>R. decussatus</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	$\frac{SS}{SST} \times 100$	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Season	2	1.814	13.5	0.907	4.97	0.002 *
Tide	1	0.033	2.4	0.033	0.07	0.80
Spawning zone	5	8.381	62.2	1.680	9.19	0.001 *
Season x Tide	2	0.001	0.01	0.001	0.001	1.00
Season x Spawning zone	10	0.016	0.1	0.002	1.76	0.14
Tide x Spawning zone	5	2.927	21.7	0.585	2.70	0.04 *
Total		13.17				

<i>R. philippinarum</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	$\frac{SS}{SST} \times 100$	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Season	2	2.140	8.0	1.068	3.90	0.04 *
Tide	1	0.258	0.9	0.258	0.37	0.55
Spawning zone	6	19.26	71.9	3.209	21.84	0.0001 ***
Season x Tide	2	0.061	0.2	0.181	0.17	0.89
Season x Spawning zone	12	3.190	11.9	0.262	1.78	0.12
Tide x Spawning zone	6	1.879	7.0	0.313	1.69	0.16
Total		26.78				

Table 4 – Multifactorial analysis of variance observed in recruitment. Three explanatory variables are considered: Tide amplitude (at which the runs start: neap or spring tide) and Season (at which the run executes; spring, summer and autumn were the seasons considered, governed by different predominating winds) which account for different hydrodynamic conditions and the Spawning zone from where the particles or eggs are released. Df: degrees of freedom, the sum of squares (SS) and the mean sum of square (MS) are estimates of the variance attributed to the explanatory variable. The ratio between SS and SST (total sum of squares) x 100 represents the contribution in percentage of the each factor to the overall variance. F is the statistic of the analysis of variance and the p-value corresponds to the probability that there is no difference in means between the different levels of the explanatory variable, and therefore significant effects can be deduced from $p < 0.05$ highlighted by an asterisks (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.001$; *** = $p < 0.0001$).

“Season and winds

Regarding spawning season, the highest recruitments of both species’ larvae were observed in summer, with predominating NE winds (Figure 1d) which aided the retention of larvae in the western and southern flats of the Bay (Figures 5b,e). These wind currents in summer also helped to generate more frequent connections between the northwestern spawning grounds and the southwestern nursery grounds (Figure 6). Regarding these connections between grounds, the most robust ones (i.e. more than 30 % of the total larvae recruited in a given nursery ground originating from a given spawning site, green and black rectangles) occurred more frequently

for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus* and particularly in summer at neap tides. Conversely, a limited recruitment was observed in spring (northward currents) (Figures 5a,d) and in Autumn (eastward currents) (Figures 5c,f) corresponding to weaker connections between grounds, particularly at spring tides (Figure 6).

Figure 5 – Spatial representation of predicted recruitment for *R. decussatus* in spring (a), summer (b) and autumn (c) scenarios and for *R. philippinarum* in the same scenarios respectively (d, e, f). Rectangles represent spawning zones and dots represent larvae recruited coming from their respective same color spawning zone. Colors used are identical to those given in Figure 2.

Figure 6 – Connectivity matrices adapted from Savina et al. (2010) for the 3 seasonal scenarios (spring, summer and autumn) and 2 tidal scenarios (neap and spring tides) simulated for *R. decussatus* (A) and *R. philippinarum* (B). The colors indicates the percentage of the total larvae recruited in a given nursery ground (x-axis) coming from each spawning ground (y-axis).

Spawning zones

Regarding zones, for *R. decussatus* larvae released from the western and southern zones of the Bay, Raos and Astillero respectively, showed the highest proportions of recruited individuals, particularly in summer (Figure 7a). This higher retention within the Bay when spawning occurs in southern zones is demonstrated in Video S2 (see supplementary information) as mentioned above. Moreover, although Cubas Outer, in the north, was not a very successful spawning ground it was significant in terms of absolute values of larvae recruited, owing to the high number of eggs released (Table 2). For this species, the interaction between the spawning zone and tides was significant. Thus, for instance, when eggs were released in Cubas Outer, the final recruitment was significantly higher at spring tide than at neap tide, while when spawning occurred in southern zones (Astillero or Elechas) recruitment was higher at neap tide than at spring tide (Table 2). For *R. philippinarum*, larvae released from the southern Bay (Astillero and Solía-Tijero) showed the highest recruitment rates (Figure 7b) and these were also the major spawning grounds in terms of the number of individuals recruited. Moreover, this species showed similar patterns regarding tide-zone effect (although not statistically significant) (Table 2 and Table 4), together with a significantly higher number and the most robust connections, which occurred at neap tides (Figure 6).

Figure 7 –Success in recruitment of each spawning ground in terms of final recruitment within the whole Bay, presented by means of predicted final recruitment (%) in different seasonal scenarios (spring, summer and autumn) for (a) *R. decussatus* and (b) *R. philippinarum*. The error bars represent the \pm SE of the mean recruitment of neap and spring tide scenarios.

Major nursery grounds and connectivity with spawning grounds

The predicted major current nursery grounds in the Bay of Santander were (1) Cubas Outer in the northeastern grounds of the estuary with ~ 80 recruiters/ m^2 and Raos (17 recruiters/ m^2) in the central western flats for *R. decussatus* and (2) Solía-Tijero in the southern inner zones of the Bay (240 recruiters/ m^2) and Cubas Outer in the northeastern area of the bay and Astillero grounds with 50 and 40 recruiters/ m^2 , respectively, for *R. philippinarum* (Figure 8). The predicted recruitment density for the whole Bay in highly suitable areas (i.e. the sum of individuals recruited in cells with habitat suitability index (HSI) >75 divided by the total area of the nursery grounds) was considerably higher for *R. philippinarum* with 50 recruiters/ m^2 than for *R. decussatus* with 17 recruiters/ m^2 , as a result of a higher retention of larvae within the Bay and a smaller area of highly suitable habitat for recruitment for *R. philippinarum* (317 Hectares) compared with *R. decussatus* (407 Hectares) (see Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013).

Figure 8 – Predicted recruitment density in nursery grounds (Habitat suitability index, HSI>75), calculated as the sum of recruitment of larvae coming from all spawning grounds at different seasons and tidal scenarios and divided by the area of the nursery ground.

Regarding the most important nursery grounds estimated in this study (Figure 8), for *R. decussatus* Cubas Outer nursery ground can be considered a self-recruitment ground in spring at spring tide, while it received “allochthonous” larvae from Cubas Inner in this season at neap tides and also in Autumn at spring tides (Figure 6a). Additionally, Raos also exhibited self-recruitment behavior, except in Summer and Autumn at neap tide. For *R. philippinarum*, Solía-Tijero and Astillero displayed self-recruitment behavior although they received recruiters from several zones, particularly at neap tide when retention within the Bay is higher (Figure 6b). Also, for this species, Cubas Outer received significant amounts of larvae coming from Cubas Inner and Elechas in Summer and Autumn. Finally, the most isolated nursery was Cubas Inner for both species, considering that it did not recruit larvae from any of the spawning sites.”

Section 3.5 & Figure 7; I am afraid that the authors make a mistake in their result analysis provided in Figure 7. Indeed, according to the tables S1a & b, the results presented in Figure 7A seem related to the settled larvae and not to the recruited larvae. This modifies notably the result interpretation (see figures below which give the two results: settled and recruited, data used coming from the Table S1a provided by authors.).

I suggest to fix it and improve the result interpretation accordingly.

We have corrected the mistake in the Figure 7A (now also Figure 7A, see previous response) and consequently the results interpretation in section 3.4 (subsection spawning zones) in the reviewed manuscript (see lines 514-530, focus on lines in bold).

“Spawning zones

Regarding zones, for *R. decussatus* larvae released from the western and southern zones of the Bay, **Raos and Astillero respectively, showed the highest proportions of recruited individuals, particularly in summer (Figure 7a)**. This higher retention within the Bay when spawning occurs in southern zones is demonstrated in Video S2 (see supplementary information) as mentioned above. Moreover, although Cubas Outer, in the north, was not a very successful spawning ground it was significant in terms of absolute values of larvae recruited, owing to the high number of eggs released (Table 2). For this species, the interaction between the spawning zone and tides was significant. Thus, for instance, when eggs were released in Cubas Outer, the final recruitment was significantly higher at spring tide than at neap tide, while when spawning occurred in southern zones (Astillero or Elechas) recruitment was higher at neap tide than at spring tide (Table 2). For *R. philippinarum*, larvae released from the southern Bay (Astillero and Solfa-Tijero) showed the highest recruitment rates (Figure 7b) and these were also the major spawning grounds in terms of the number of individuals recruited. Moreover, this species showed similar patterns regarding tide-zone effect (although not statistically significant) (Table 2 and Table 4), together with a significantly higher number and the most robust connections, which occurred at neap tides (Figure 6).

In the Table 2, the p-value is informative, but the contribution of each factor to the total variance may be a more relevant index in a comparison purpose.

We included the F statistic for this purpose but in order to incorporate a have a more interpretable index to explain contribution (in percentage) of each factor to the total variance we decided to include the ratio between the Sum of Squares and the Total Sum of Squares (SST). See Table 4 in the reviewed manuscript for a better resolution.

<i>R. decussatus</i>	Recruitment succes (%)					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	$\frac{SS}{SST} \times 100$	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Season	2	1.814	13.5	0.907	4.97	0.002 *
Tide	1	0.033	2.4	0.033	0.07	0.80
Spawning zone	5	8.381	62.2	1.680	9.19	0.001 *
Season x Tide	2	0.001	0.01	0.001	0.001	1.00
Season x Spawning zone	10	0.016	0.1	0.002	1.76	0.14
Tide x Spawning zone	5	2.927	21.7	0.585	2.70	0.04 *
Total		13.17				

<i>R. philippinarum</i>	Recruitment succes (%)					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	$\frac{SS}{SST} \times 100$	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Season	2	2.140	8.0	1.068	3.90	0.04 *
Tide	1	0.258	0.9	0.258	0.37	0.55
Spawning zone	6	19.26	71.9	3.209	21.84	0.0001 ***
Season x Tide	2	0.061	0.2	0.181	0.17	0.89
Season x Spawning zone	12	3.190	11.9	0.262	1.78	0.12
Tide x Spawning zone	6	1.879	7.0	0.313	1.69	0.16
Total		26.78				

“Table 4 – Multifactorial analysis of variance observed in recruitment. Three explanatory variables are considered: Tide amplitude (at which the runs start: neap or spring tide) and Season (at which the run executes; spring, summer and autumn were the seasons considered, governed by different predominating winds) which account for different hydrodynamic conditions and the Spawning zone from where the particles or eggs are released. Df: degrees of freedom, the sum of squares (SS) and the mean sum of square (MS) are estimates of the variance attributed to the explanatory variable. The ratio between SS and SST (total sum of squares) x 100 represents the contribution in percentage of the each factor to the overall variance. F is the statistic of the analysis of variance and the p-value corresponds to the probability that there is no difference in means between the different levels of the explanatory variable, and therefore significant effects can be deduced from $p < 0.05$ highlighted by an asterisks (*= $p < 0.05$; **= $p < 0.001$; ***= $p < 0.0001$).”

We described results regarding the variance attributed to each explanatory variable in (1) results section and in (2) discussion section (see in bold)

(1) Lines 485-494

“3.4. Influential factors on recruitment and connectivity between grounds

Recruitment data (i.e., the percentage of the total released eggs successfully recruited) were first log-transformed to achieve normality and homogeneity of variance. The factorial ANOVA results presented in Table 4 shows that season (i.e. predominating winds) and the location of the spawning zone have significant effects on the final recruitment success of both clam species. **The location of spawning zone contributed more importantly to the overall variance.** Additionally, the tidal phase (spring or neap) at the spawning moment had no significant effect on the recruitment of either of the two species. However, the interaction between these two factors had a significant effect for *R. decussatus* (Table 4) and a tidal effect on connection patterns between spawning and nursery grounds can be appreciated (Figure 8). “

(2) Lines 622-653

“Season, spawning ground location and tidal effect

The results suggest that the location of the source populations and wind-induced currents have significant effects on the recruitment of both species (Table 4). **The complex configuration of the Bay of Santander with both inner/narrower areas and more open tidal flats, where spawning grounds are located, appears to have the greatest impact on the success of larval retention and recruitment, explaining ~60-70 % of the total variance of recruitment.** Herbert et al. (2012) found similar results when modelling *R. philippinarum* larval transport in Pool Harbour (England) which contains different embayments. Hinckley et al. (2001) highlighted the importance of spawning location and timing to successful walleye pollock *Theragra chalcogramma* larval transport to nursery areas. Moreover, Rigal et al. (2010) demonstrated that the interaction between spawning location and hydrodynamics have important effects on retention of the gastropod *Crepidula fornicata* within a coastal bay. Wind advection has been considered to have important effects in larval distribution in large (~1000

km²) and vertically stratified bays (Hinata and Tomisu, 2005) and open coastal areas (e.g. Bas et al., 2009; Ayata et al., 2010) where wind-induced currents are usually important together with water movements due to tides. **Therefore, although initially it may be assumed that in a small estuary like the Bay of Santander this wind effect would not be important, our results suggest that wind-induced hydrodynamics is a factor to be considered, being responsible for the ~ 8 – 14 % of the total variance of recruitment.** Other studies have also shown that wind effects are important in larval distribution (Suzuki et al., 2002; Leis, 2006; Ayata et al., 2010) and under some conditions the wind-induced physical structure could be an important mechanism of retention of invertebrate larvae (Epifanio et al., 1989; Verdier-Bonnet et al., 1997).

The interaction between spawning zone location and tidal phase at the spawning moment showed an effect on final recruitment, being statistically significant for *R. decussatus* and explaining 22 % of the total variance. Recruitment was higher at spring tides in the outer zone of Cubas, probably due to the return of larvae to the mouth of estuary helped by tides, and higher at neap tides in the inner southern zones since neap tides limited flushing larvae out of estuary. Similarly, recruitment of larvae retention of crabs or clam larvae is higher when spawning occurs at neap tides than at spring tides (Forward, 1987, Gove and Paula, 2000; Chícharo and Chícharo, 2000:2001a) and the ingress of crab larvae in a estuary and settlement is higher at times, ranging from several days after spring tide to near the neap tide (Roegner et al., 2007).

Section 3.6; P24 - L41-43, the authors give new information on the suitable area for the two species. This is related to the ENFA and HSI analysis, which is not clearly presented. I suggest giving this information earlier in the method section so as to support the discussion and result interpretation.

We agree with this comment and in consequence we decided to include a reference to the new Figure 2 (in bold) where the spatial information of habitat suitability was presented. We also change the reference from Bidegain et al., under review” to Bidegain (2013) (in bold) which has been published recently. A better description of ENFA analysis is presented in methods section as was commented above in the responses to the method section (see lines 539-545).

“The predicted recruitment density for the whole Bay in highly suitable areas (i.e. the sum of individuals recruited in cells with habitat suitability index (HSI) >75 divided by the total area of the nursery grounds) was considerably higher for *R. philippinarum* with 50 recruiters/m² than for *R. decussatus* with 17 recruiters/m², as a result of a higher retention of larvae within the Bay and a smaller area of highly suitable habitat for recruitment for *R. philippinarum* (317 Hectares) compared with *R. decussatus* (407 Hectares) (see **Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013**).”

Section 3.7; P25 - L15; "for *R. philippinarum* three or more robust connections occurred in all scenarios except in autumn at spring tide" I disagree, this is true for all the scenarios since there is 3 connection >60 and 2 connections >30 in autumn at spring tide.

Note that in Figure 6 (before, Figure 10), the black colors (> 60) situated in the diagonal line are not robust connections since they represent that the larvae recruited in the nursery ground mainly comes from the same ground. It is a “self-connection” and that is way we did not consider it as a connection between grounds.

Discussion

In the discussion, I was frustrated to find too little thing on the inter-specific comparison, notably related to the habitat suitability, which is the main originality of this work.

What could be the limitations of this kind of approach, in the choice of the HSI thresholds for example?

Does the difference in the validation agreement between the two species could be related to the habitat suitability or to another factor?

I suggest improving the discussion on this specific point in order to give more information to the reader on the model sensitivity to the habitat-suitability.

The effect of the PLD appeared consistent between the two species, but the effect of the specific vertical swimming behaviors is not clear.

Is there really a high effect of the vertical displacement? What would be the results without any swimming sub-model?

The results do not provide information on this topic and the discussion either.

I suggest to improve the discussion section related to the PLD and to the swimming behavior by distinguishing the two, by reorganizing the paragraphs P-28 and 29, and by giving more insight on the swimming effect.

We agree with these comments and we decided to rewrite the discussion and conclusion sections in order to answer reviewer 1's questions. For this purpose, we reorganize and rewrite the discussion section including subsections such as "*Swimming behavior and habitat suitability*", "*Planctonic larval duration*" and "*Major spawning and nursery zones*" where these questions related with HS and PLD are answered or suggestions are included. These subsections have been rewritten based on new analysis done by comparing results obtained by LARVAHS and the two variations of the model (without behavior and without habitat suitability). See the (1) following rewritten 2.4.section regarding this analysis and (2) mentioned discussion subsections:

(1) Material and methods. Lines 342-348

" 2.4. LARVAHS model evaluation

A preliminary evaluation of the LARVAHS model to predict recruitment of clams was conducted in two nursery grounds (Elechas and Raos) by comparing predictions with observed data. Moreover, two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of larval behavior and habitat suitability in recruitment: (1) a LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) a LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model)."

(2) Discussion.

"Swimming behavior and habitat suitability (Lines 575-607)

In order to analyze the role of swimming behavior and habitat suitability submodels in recruitment predictions we considered it necessary to compare estimations obtained by the LARVAHS model with those obtained by two variations of the model (i.e. a NO HS model, using settled larvae without a habitat suitability- recruitment submodel and (ii) a NO BEHAVIOR model, a passive behavior model that ignores swimming ability. This comparative analysis showed that these two variations of the LARVAHS model did not adequately forecast seasonal patterns and no significant correlations were observed with field data. On one hand, the absence of habitat suitability led to a strong overestimation of recruitment, since the important post settlement mortality associated with recruitment of benthic invertebrates (Hunt and Scheibling, 1997) was not integrated in the NO HS model and, consequently, all larvae settled within the Bay survived. On the other hand, the NO BEHAVIOR model with a passive behavior of larvae underestimated the observed recruitment more significantly than the LARVAHS model. This result suggests that the incorporation of swimming behavior favored larvae retention within the Bay, influencing their encounter with a suitable habitat for recruitment (Table 3). According to Kuroda (2005), this vertical-down "migration" is essential to prevent all larvae from being dragged into offshore areas at ebb tide. This finding is consistent with recent observations by Herbert et al. (2012) for *R. philippinarum*, and such vertical swimming behavior also has a major impact on the distribution in tidal estuaries of other species which broadcast larvae, such as crustaceans (Zeng and Naylor, 1996) and other bivalves (North et al., 2008).

Regarding specific differences, recruitment of larvae within the Bay was significantly higher for *R. philippinarum* with all the models (Table 3). In the case of the LARVAHS model, this outcome was remarkable, since we considered larger areas of suitable habitat for recruitment of *R. decussatus* compared with *R. philippinarum* (see Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013). This suggests that retention of larvae might be a more critical determinant of final recruitment than the difference in suitable habitat surface area between species. When we modeled larvae dispersal without incorporating habitat suitability, the differences in recruitment between species were more significant (i.e. higher t-statistic values) than for the LARVAHS or NO BEHAVIOR models, suggesting that specific differences in post larval mortality associated with differences in highly suitable surface areas has a stronger effect on recruitment than specific differences in planktonic larval duration (PLD) (or each larval phase duration).

Planktonic larval duration (Lines 609-620)

Results obtained with the NO BEHAVIOR (or passive swimming) model showed that the PLD had an effect on larvae retention and final recruitment within the estuary. A longer PLD of *R. decussatus* has a significant negative effect on larval retention, resulting in higher mortality rates and lower recruitment success than *R. philippinarum*. Thus, the longer PLD of *R. decussatus* over *R. philippinarum* seems to be the main reason for the higher larval dispersion and lower recruitment rates for this species. This result is consistent with the outcomes of the few biophysical models that have tested for it and found significant effects of PDL on larval transport (Edwards et al., 2007). For example, increasing the PLD significantly of brittle star (echinoderms) decreases the larval retention in the natal region and increases the larval mortality (Lefebvre et al., 2003). Moreover, a reduction in the PDL of scallop larvae decreases their displacement distance (Tremblay et al., 1994).

.....

Major spawning and nursery zones (see lines 660-667)

....However, the results obtained in this study should be taken with caution since the selection of a high HSI threshold (i.e. 75) to define spawning or nursery grounds is a simplification of the reality in easily delimited grounds, adopted in order to avoid overlapping and facilitate interpretation and analysis of results. Lower thresholds may lead to larger grounds but with lower estimations of average spawner adult densities or recruitment rates. Therefore, depending on the management needs, a combination of detection of the main hot spot(s), delimitation of larger sanctuaries and interpretability of results should be considered in order to select the appropriate HSI threshold.

.....

To answer questions or better understand aspects regarding discussion section Reviewer 2 could also see response to results section “3.1. LARVASH model evaluation” above.

- **Reviewer 2:**

General comments

While I was excited to read this paper as it is similar to my own research in larval dispersal modelling, I was disappointed both by the length and lack of cohesiveness of the paper, and because the authors have failed to emphasize in their very long paper the results using LARVAHS that are new and innovative.

We have read the entire manuscript again and agree with this comment regarding length and lack of cohesiveness, repetitive commentaries, and emphasis on innovativeness of the model. Hence, in order to correct this we decided to rewrite methodology, results and discussion sections and connect them appropriately. Moreover, we have shortened the manuscript considerably (2200 words), avoiding large descriptions about hydrodynamics and more focusing the manuscript on habitat suitability and model sensitivity issues which are key results of the study. We also tried to not emphasizing the innovativeness of the approach.

The paper does have potential, but requires an extensive rewrite to clarify how integrating larval suitability maps actually makes a difference (or doesn't?) in hydrodynamic models of larval dispersal.

We also agree with this comment and in consequence we decided to evaluate the model not only comparing observed data and predicted data of recruitment using LARVAHS. Two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of larval behavior and habitat suitability, integrated in LARVAHS, on recruitment: (1) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model). We described this analysis as follows in section 2.4 (see lines 342-367):

“2.4. LARVAHS model evaluation

“A preliminary evaluation of the LARVAHS model to predict recruitment of clams was conducted in two nursery grounds (Elechas and Raos) by comparing predictions with observed data. Moreover, two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of larval behavior and habitat suitability in recruitment: (1) a LARVAHS model with no behavior

submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) a LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model).”

Results of this analysis are presented and discussed in the (1) results subsection 3.1.and (2) discussion subsection “*Swimming behavior and habitat suitability*” as follows:

(1) 3. Results

“3.1. LARVAHS model evaluation (see lines 417-438)

The LARVAHS model estimations were evaluated in two zones (Raos and Elechas) and for the three studied seasons (Spring, Summer, Autumn) revealing that the predicted recruitment density values were lower than the mean observed values in general, for both species and all seasons (see black circles in Figure 3), except in the summer scenario in Raos. The generalized underestimation of the LARVAHS model was not significantly different between species considering that when underestimation occurred it was $3.62 (\pm 1.47)$ (\pm SD) individuals/m² for *R. decussatus* (Figures 3a,b) and $3.28 (\pm 2.09)$ individuals/m² for *R. philippinarum* (Figures 3c,d). Figure 3 shows that the seasonal variability in recruitment patterns was detected by the LARVAHS model, obtaining significant correlation values between observed and predicted recruitment density for *R. decussatus* (Spearman’s $R=0.89$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 4.1$, $p=0.0$) and *R. philippinarum* (Spearman’s $R=0.94$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 5.6$, $p=0.005$) which involves a good qualitative fit of the model to the in situ measured data.

However, seasonal variability in recruitment was not detected by the two variations of the LARVAHS model and the correlation values obtained between predictions and observed data were not significant, neither for the NO BEHAVIOR model (*R. philippinarum*, $R=0.07$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 0.14$, $p=0.89$; *R. philippinarum*, $R=0.70$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 1.94$, $p=0.12$), nor for the NO HS model (*R. philippinarum*, $R=0.46$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 1.05$, $p=0.35$; *R. philippinarum*, $R=0.430$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 0.95$, $p=0.40$). Moreover, the NO BEHAVIOR model results underestimated the observed data more significantly than the LARVHAS model in all cases for both species, and using the NO HS model the overestimation was highly appreciable (Figure 3).”

“Figure 3 – Observed (white quadrates) and predicted recruitment (individuals/m²) obtained with LARVAHS model (black circles), NO BEHAVIOR model (gray triangles) and NO HS model (black crosses) are presented. Results are presented for Spring, Summer and Autumn season scenarios, for *R. decussatus* (A, B) and *R. philippinarum* (C, D) in Elechas and Raos sites respectively. Error bars for observed data represent the standard error.”

“3.2. Simulation results data (see lines 442-464)

Results of the 78 runs, 36 runs for *R. decussatus* and 42 runs for *R. philippinarum* are presented in Table 2 for the LARVAHS model and the two described variations of this model: the LARVAHS model without the behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and the LARVAHS model without the habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). For each spawning zone the particles released were different, according to the zone extension and the density of adults clams. Thus, for *R. decussatus* Cubas the Outer ground, with $\sim 800000 \times 10^5$ eggs released, was the most “egg productive” spawning zone, followed by Astillero and Pedreña with $\sim 188000 \times 10^5$ and $\sim 164000 \times 10^5$ eggs released, respectively. Additionally, the Pedreña spawning zone, with 963000×10^5 eggs released was the most productive zone for *R. philippinarum*, followed by Elechas with $\sim 333000 \times 10^5$ eggs released.

Run	Season	Tide	Zone of release	Released (n)		Recruited LARVAHS (%)		Recruited NO BEHAVIOR (%)		Recruited NO HS (%)	
				<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>
1-37	Spring	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.036	0.144	0.009	0.027	0.461	1.027
2-38	Spring	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.009	0.011	0.001	0.002	0.282	0.639
3-39	Spring	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.062	0.036	0.019	0.000	0.690	0.804
4-40	Spring	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.215	0.460
5-41	Spring	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.005	0.015	0.006	0.030	0.191	0.628
6-42	Spring	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.004	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.234	0.384
43	Spring	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.808	–	0.410	–	1.587
7-44	Spring	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.014	0.089	0.007	0.051	0.337	0.818
8-45	Spring	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.203	0.353
9-46	Spring	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.030	0.006	0.008	0.000	0.439	0.722
10-47	Spring	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.115	0.242
11-48	Spring	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.056	0.297	0.018	0.390	0.187	0.717
12-49	Spring	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.011	0.052	0.009	0.035	0.200	0.524
50	Spring	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.676	–	0.290	–	1.514
13-51	Summer	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.222	0.687	0.029	0.350	1.480	1.623
14-52	Summer	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.034	0.200	0.026	0.230	0.994	1.225
15-53	Summer	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.089	0.064	0.021	0.074	1.219	1.319
16-54	Summer	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.024	0.051	0.021	0.220	0.914	0.909
17-55	Summer	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.015	0.536	0.766
18-56	Summer	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.009	0.052	0.013	0.080	0.722	0.908
57	Summer	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.115	–	0.360	–	1.718
19-58	Summer	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.084	0.260	0.070	0.210	0.973	1.202
20-59	Summer	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.011	0.021	0.022	0.097	0.898	0.920
21-60	Summer	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.121	0.032	0.038	0.068	1.393	1.231
22-61	Summer	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.013	0.016	0.020	0.070	0.934	0.890
23-62	Summer	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.020	0.015	0.002	0.019	0.964	0.951
24-63	Summer	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.052	0.002	0.052	0.951	0.978
64	Summer	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.006	–	0.090	–	1.746
25-65	Autumn	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.104	0.447	0.013	0.260	0.934	1.256
26-66	Autumn	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.016	0.041	0.007	0.290	0.352	0.589
27-67	Autumn	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.018	0.038	0.062	0.110	0.634	0.844
28-68	Autumn	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.308	0.643
29-69	Autumn	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.000	0.007	0.001	0.001	0.392	0.699
30-70	Autumn	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.035	0.009	0.068	0.378	0.681
71	Autumn	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.149	–	0.310	–	1.769
31-72	Autumn	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.021	0.101	0.007	0.069	0.358	0.817
32-73	Autumn	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.248	0.412
33-74	Autumn	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.038	0.040	0.010	0.002	0.809	0.790
34-75	Autumn	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.006	0.001	0.001	0.288	0.553
35-76	Autumn	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.006	0.007	0.002	0.001	0.292	0.810
36-77	Autumn	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.007	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.396	0.699
78	Autumn	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.824	–	0.190	–	1.722

Table 2 – Predicted recruitment scores (%) for simulated *R. decussatus* (*R. dec*) and *R. philippinarum* (*R. phil.*) eggs released (= released particles x 10⁵) from each spawning zone (Astillero, Elechas, Raos, Pedreña, Cubas Outer, Cubas Inner, Solía-Tijero) in each seasonal (spring, summer and autumn) and tidal amplitude (spring or neap tides) scenario, for a total of 36 runs for *R. decussatus* (1-36, left digit in column 1) and 42 for *R. philippinarum* (37-78, right digit in column 1). Results computed by (1) LARVAHS model, (2) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS) are presented.

The recruitment percentages were very low for the LARVAHS model and also for the two variations of the model, due mainly to high natural mortality rates and low retention of larvae within the Bay, or to settlement in unsuitable zones. Recruitment success was significantly higher for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus* (see Table 3) for LARVAHS (df=76, t=-3.38, p=0.001) and also for the two model variations (No Behavior, df= 76, t=-2.45, p=0.01; No HS, df= 76, t=-4.48, p=0.0003). The analysis of the variance of recruitment success between models showed significant differences between all of the models for both species, with the significantly highest recruitment for the NO HS model and the lowest recruitment percentages for the NO BEHAVIOR model (Table 3).

Species	Recruitment succes (%)			ANOVA test				
	LARVAHS	NO BEHAVIOR	NO HS	df	SS	MS	F	p
<i>R. decussatus</i>	0.03 ±0.01 A	0.01 ±0.002 B	0.58 ±0.06 C	2	75.8	37.9	122.3	***
<i>R. philippinarum</i>	0.20 ±0.05 A	0.11 ±0.02 B	0.93 ±0.06 C	2.0	70.0	35.0	37.7	***

Table 3 – Recruitment success (% , Mean ± SE) for *R. decussatus* (n= 36 simulations) and *R. philippinarum* (n=42) obtained using (i) the LARVAHS model, which incorporates larval behavior and habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, (ii) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and) (iii)LARVAHS model with no Habitat Suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). Results of the analysis of variance between recruitment obtained using different models are presented at right (*= p<0.05; **= p<0.001; ***= p <0.0001). Tukey HSD – test results are presented by letters (A, B, C) placed after each model mean. If any two means have at least one letter in common, they are not significantly different.

(2) Discussion (see lines 565-607)

“Swimming behavior and habitat suitability

In order to analyze the role of swimming behavior and habitat suitability submodels in recruitment predictions we considered it necessary to compare estimations obtained by the LARVAHS model with those obtained by two variations of the model (i.e. a NO HS model, using settled larvae without a habitat suitability- recruitment submodel and (ii) a NO BEHAVIOR model, a passive behavior model that ignores swimming ability. This comparative analysis showed that these two variations of the LARVAHS model did not adequately forecast seasonal patterns and no significant correlations were observed with field data. On one hand, the absence of habitat suitability led to a strong overestimation of recruitment, since the important post settlement mortality associated with recruitment of benthic invertebrates (Hunt and Scheibling, 1997) was not integrated in the NO HS model and, consequently, all larvae settled within the Bay survived. On the other hand, the NO BEHAVIOR model with a passive behavior of larvae underestimated the observed recruitment more significantly than the LARVAHS model. This result suggests that the incorporation of swimming behavior favored larvae retention within the Bay, influencing their encounter with a suitable habitat for recruitment (Table 3). According to Kuroda (2005), this vertical-down "migration" is essential to prevent all larvae from being dragged into offshore areas at ebb tide.

This finding is consistent with recent observations by Herbert et al. (2012) for *R. philippinarum*, and such vertical swimming behavior also has a major impact on the distribution in tidal estuaries of other species which broadcast larvae, such as crustaceans (Zeng and Naylor, 1996) and other bivalves (North et al., 2008).

Regarding specific differences, recruitment of larvae within the Bay was significantly higher for *R. philippinarum* with all the models (Table 3). In the case of the LARVAHS model, this outcome was remarkable, since we considered larger areas of suitable habitat for recruitment of *R. decussatus* compared with *R. philippinarum* (see Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013). This suggests that retention of larvae might be a more critical determinant of final recruitment than the difference in suitable habitat surface area between species. When we modeled larvae dispersal without incorporating habitat suitability, the differences in recruitment between species were more significant (i.e. higher t-statistic values) than for the LARVAHS or NO BEHAVIOR models, suggesting that specific differences in post larval mortality associated with differences in highly suitable surface areas has a stronger effect on recruitment than specific differences in planktonic larval duration (PLD) (or each larval phase duration).”

My primary concern is the length and lack of cohesiveness of the manuscript. It was tedious to read, far too long for a journal submission, and had far too many extraneous figures.

As we mentioned above we agree with this comment and decided to rewrite methodology, results and discussion sections and connect them appropriately. Moreover, we have shortened the manuscript in ~ 2200 words, particularly introduction, results and discussion sections and combined or eliminated extraneous figures.

The authors should carefully consider what needs to be included in the manuscript, and which figures have already been presented (e.g., much of the hydrodynamic figures showing tidal and wind currents can be described in the text and/or reduced to one figure (eg Figure 5 which simulations don't appear different enough to warrant presentation of all three seasons - instead I would suggest that Fig 5 is combined with Fig 1 - A=bathymetry; B= tidal currents (one example only, with a sentence in text to clarify similarity of all three seasons); C=wind (one example only, with a sentence in text to clarify pattern similarity of all seasons, and that the third season was substantially lower in magnitude, but same general spatial pattern).

We agree with this comment and also the ones related to this figure done by reviewer 1. IN consequence we decided to add an overall map of the coastline of Spain and France, the scale, the north arrow and the name of the main river (see Figure 1A). We also decided to include in the same figure (following the suggestions of reviewer 2) the hydrodynamic patterns: we include tidal-river mean annual currents (Figure 2B) considering tidal force is similar for all seasons and river outputs were low in general (< 2 m³/s) and not significantly different between seasons (Bidegain et al., 2013) and wind current seasonal patterns to show different predominating current directions in each season (Figures 2C-E).

“Figure 1 - Study area for the model: Bay of Santander estuary and adjacent waters located in the northern coast of Spain (Gulf of Biscay). Bathymetry (m) data of the modeled area are presented. Tidal-river annual mean currents (ms^{-1}) (a, b, c) and wind currents (d, e, f) for Spring, Summer and Autumn scenarios.”

Figure 3 - not necessary, and presumably this is in a published manuscript of the model validation. Basically, the manuscript is supposed to be about the larval behaviour - and instead the details of the hydrodynamics which have been presumably validated and presented elsewhere - dominate this manuscript and leave little space available for the more innovative and important results.

We agree with this comment regarding the details presented about hydrodynamics and decided to eliminate figure 3.

A key piece of missing information is what is the actual difference in model results when modelling with and without the suitability map. It is unclear how much the suitability map vs. the hydrodynamics are driving the model results. Key comparisons should include settlement spatial variability and changes in success rates of particles (both within sites, and in total, for example, does adding a suitability map reduce total settlement success by 50%? Does it increase settlement in suitable areas by X%? Does it result in less larvae transported outside of the model region?).

We also agree with this comment and as mentioned, in consequence, we decided to evaluate the model not only comparing observed data and predicted data of recruitment using LARVAHS. Two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of larval behavior and habitat suitability, integrated in LARVAHS, on recruitment: (1) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) **LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model)**.

See evaluation, results and discussion paragraphs related with this issue in the second response

to reviewer 2 (pp. 27-32 in this document)

Specific comments

Introduction should be shortened by half. As example. On page 6, paragraph starting with "Recently, Herbert et al. (2012)..". Could be shorted to a list of key sentences of key approaches taken in past research, each with references associated rather than this disjunct set of independent sentences each describing individual papers.

Also, I note the authors don't have correct understanding of the approaches and models used in many of these studies. Further in the introduction and discussion, the authors suggest their work is particularly novel, and only few approaches have done similar, and none of them adequately. I disagree - particularly as they cite many of the studies with habitat suitability models in their paper, and suggest they might reread the literature to better understand differences between hydrodynamic approaches, and those that have included subroutines for larval behaviour or habitat suitability (or both).

We agree with the comment regarding to shorten the introduction and rewriting the paragraph on page 6. In consequence, we have shortened the introduction section in ~300 words and rewritten the three following paragraphs including the one mentioned by reviewer 2. Moreover we hope that these rewritten paragraphs may clarify our understanding of different models' approaches.

Regarding, the novelty of our study, we cited several models including habitat suitability- based settlement submodels, which considered presence of coast or adults or an unique environmental variable as a condition for settlement. The novelty of this study is that we integrated a set of environmental variables using ENFA in order to have a more refined settlement-recruitment submodel. See the rewritten paragraphs in lines 103-122 as follows:

"...Commercial and widely distributed mollusks such as clams, oysters or abalones and crabs or fishes have been the main objective species of biophysical models. Larval dispersion of these species have been modeled assuming to behave as passive tracers of currents (Hinata and Tomisu, 2005; Hinata and Furukawa, 2006; Stephens et al., 2006; Miyake et al., 2009), incorporating larvae behavior (Herbert et al., 2012) and, in the absence of a settlement submodel, to have a competent period for settlement after planktonic larval duration was completed, or over the last three days of life. Recently, other authors have integrated settlement submodels in LDM and assumed the presence of adult oysters (North et al., 2008) or proximity of crabs to the coast (Roughan et al., 2011) as indicators of suitable zones for settlement, which by default accounted for habitat suitability. Hinrichsen, et al. (2009) assumed a minimum requirement of a unique environmental variable (i.e. oxygen saturation) for cod (*Gadus morhua*) settlement and recruitment success.

In summary, only a few biophysical models include a habitat suitability approach in their settlement subroutines, which commonly do not consider a combination of environmental variables to define the suitable habitat conditions for survival of species. The subsequent aim, beyond determining larval dispersal and simplified settlement patterns, is to move towards including habitat suitability modeling to better understand recruitment success and post settlement mortality. "

Unusual for the paper to rely on videos, when snapshots of model behaviour would be adequate at different timesteps. I would suggest that all information needs to be available in print for this manuscript, with videos to only be supplementary, but conclusions of the manuscripts can be

reached without viewing the video. For example 'Video simulations demonstrate a plume of larvae alternatively flushed in and out of the Bay with the tide (see Supp1).'

We agree with this comment and consequently we decided to move videos into supplementary information (Video S1, Video S2). Moreover, we presented in figure 4 snapshots of larval vertical dynamics extracted from the video S1. See the references to figures and videos in bold in the following paragraph (lines 468-479).

“3.3. Larval dynamics

The assumed vertical behavior of *R. decussatus* and *R. philippinarum* larvae adapted from literature (see Table 1) was correctly simulated (see **Figure 4 and Video S1, supplementary information**). During the trocophore phase, we found all larvae at the surface (Figure 4a) while D and early Umbo-stage larvae were found at surface to intermediate depths (Figure 4b). Late Umbo and early Pediveliger-stage larvae were found uniformly distributed at all depths (Figure 4c), while late Pediveliger larvae were observed close to the bottom (Figure 4d). Regarding spatial dynamics, **Video S2 (see supplementary information)** helps to visualize larval pool movements and shows the plume of larvae alternatively flushed in and out of the Bay with the tidal currents, and a differentiated retention of larvae depending on the zone of spawning. Nevertheless, final recruitment spatial patterns occurring after larval dispersal and influential factors are described in later sections.”

Methods while generally too descriptive on most aspects, were too minimal for descriptions of the dynamics for the larval behaviour section of the model, including how habitat suitability was integrated with larval behaviour. Did swimming behaviour change with age (and if this was not modelled, why not?). Did swimming behaviour change within distance/when above suitable habitat beyond 'when particles were at the sea bottom'? The Tables were missing from the submitted manuscript so none of this could be evaluated to see if adequate complexity was added.

We appreciate and agree with the comment by the reviewer 2. We are sorry for not submitting the table associated to the text. In this corrected submission we include Table 1, which summarizes the behavioral considerations of the two species that were implemented into the behavior sub-model. We hope this table answers reviewer 2’s questions.

Life cycle	Life days	Life days	Swimming	Direction and movement probability	Swimming speed (mm/s)
	<i>R. decussatus</i>	<i>R. philippinarum</i>	capability		
Egg	0 – 1	0 – 1	No	0	0
Trocophore Larvae	1 – 2	1 – 2	Yes	90% chance of move up	0.5

D, Umbo Larvae	2 – 14	2 – 10	Yes	Probabilities that shift their distribution from the upper layer to the lower layer as they increase in age, from a 51% chance of move up in each time step to a 51.7% chance of swimming down (linear function of particle age).	0.5-3 (speed increases linearly with age)
Pediveliger Larvae	15 – 21	10 – 15	Yes	100% chance of move down and stay within a 1 m water column from sea-bottom. In this water column, 50% chance of move up and 50% chance of move down	3

Table 1- Summary of larval behavior for *R. decussatus* and *R. philippinarum*. It details, for egg and larval phases, the duration (life days) and the capability and the vertical swimming behavior, adapted from Suzuki et al. (2002), Kuroda (2005), Ishii et al. (2005) and North et al. (2006:2008).

The calculations of the 2D depth-averaged hydrodynamic model for tidal currents appear simplistic and unvalidated.

We agree with this comment in terms of simplicity of the model comparing with a 3-D model. However, the hydrodynamic model is a quasi 3-D model since it takes into account the different structure over the horizontal velocities along the depth. The model is validated in the same domain against observed water levels, current velocities and salinities, covering a full phase of spring and neap tides. See section 2.2.1 for more details in lines 184-191:

“2.2.1. Hydrodynamic model

Tidal current velocities were calculated by means of a two-dimensional depth-averaged hydrodynamic coastal and estuarine circulation model (H2D model; see Bárcena et al., 2012a,b and García et al., 2010a). This quasi three-dimensional model takes into account the different structure over the depth of horizontal velocities along the depth, due to wind action (Koutitas, 1988). A similar implementation, i.e. the same code, same forcing data and similar domain, has been previously calibrated and validated by López et al. (2013) against observed water levels, current velocities and salinities, covering a full phase of spring and neap tides.”

One would anticipate seasonal impacts on larval life stage, eg warmer temperatures = faster time to settlement. This does not appear to be included in the comparison between seasons.

We appreciate and agree with the comment by the reviewer but unfortunately do not have solid quantitative results about the temperature effect on both species settlement. We described the seasonal differences only in terms of different predominating winds for each season. The integration of temperature in the model will be essential in future research lines.

Model evaluation - the use of the 1mm sieve to compare recruit density vs. model simulation is incorrect. Based on larval size, a 250 micron sieve should have been used. Many of the recruits should be less than 1mm, so the results presented would show a massive time lag between settlement and what the authors sample, and the data would be irrelevant to recruitment season due to both insufficient sampling of appropriate size classes, and the likelihood of post-settlement mortality being variable between site due to site specific differences in environmental or biological (eg predators) parameters.

We agree with these insightful comments. A 250 micron sieve would have shown a less time lag between settlement and sampling and the generalized underestimation obtained with LARVAHS model comparing with observed data would be larger. However the model detects the seasonal variations quite good in qualitative terms.

In any case, we agree that readers should be made aware of this issue and so we have changed the following paragraph in conclusion section and included some lines regarding future research lines as follows (lines 711-728):

“Conclusions

The LARVAHS model may serve as a useful framework to guide quantitative investigations about settlement and recruitment predictions since it has an important focus in habitat suitability modelling-based recruitment estimations. The model predicted seasonal recruitment variability reasonably well although, like other similar models, it cannot reproduce the orders of magnitude variability since it does not include many important biological processes (e.g. specific larvae behavior, gamete fertilization success, larval mortality and growth, post-settlement mortality due to predation, etc.). Thus, future analyses should be conducted upon these results by assessing the potential contribution of these parameters. Moreover, it is essential to validate the results obtained using the model through comparison with new observed data such as larvae concentration at different levels of the water column and early recruiters (< 250 microns) density.”....

Not enough detail is provided on how habitat suitability is calculated - eg, is it based on existing spawning grounds occurring there, rather than any environmental parameter that would result in larval preferential settlement (mud vs. sand, current flow?). Referring to a submitted paper is not sufficient.

We agree with this comment (also commented by reviewer 1 and answered above) and as a result we have decided to better describe the settlement-recruitment submodel subsection within the section **2.2.2. Larval dispersal model: LARVAHS** by adding or rewriting several paragraphs dealing with determination of HS in the settlement-recruitment sub-model subsection as follows (in lines 270-298) by rewriting the whole paragraph of this subsection (see in bold environmental parameters considered to perform ENFA):

“Settlement-recruitment sub-model

We used a habitat-suitability (HS) raster-based grid to determine if a pediveliger-stage larvae encountered a suitable habitat to settle and recruit. Each cell of the grid had a HS index (HSI) which ranged from 0 to 100, with higher values being more suitable for recruitment and zero being completely unsuitable. This grid was obtained from the ecological niche factor analysis (ENFA) conducted successfully by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) for each of the studied species in the Bay of Santander obtaining reasonably good model validation results (see Figure 2a). **Different topographic (depth), physical (salinity, current velocity and sediment characteristics such as percentage of sand, gravel and silt) and chemical environmental variables (organic matter content in sediment), assumed as meaningful to the ecology and distribution of these species (e.g. Laing and Child, 1996; Vincenzi et al., 2006, Cannas, 2010) were considered, together with presence data to perform this analysis.** The integration of habitat suitability grids in the model grid was automatic since the extent of the study area and the cell size used were identical.

The minimum HSI value considered for recruitment to occur was 25, assuming a HSI value from 0 to 25 to be an unsuitable habitat for recruitment (see Figure 2a,b). For every internal time step (30 s), each pediveliger-stage particle was tested to determine if it was at the sea-bottom. When it was at the bottom, the sub-model checked if the HSI on this cell was greater than 25 and in that case, the particle settled, or stopped moving. When the HSI was lower than 25, the particle continued swimming. Finally, if the particle did not encounter a cell of $HSI > 25$ at the end of the pediveliger-stage, the particle dies.

Once a given particle settled in a cell, the HSI value of this cell was assumed as the survival probability of the particle. To perform the larval recruitment, the model generated a random number between 0 and 100. If this random number was lower than the survival probability of the particle (the HSI), the settled particle survived and it was successfully recruited. On the contrary, if the random number was greater than the survival probability of the particle, the settled particle died.”

Moreover, as it was suggested by reviewer 1 we include a map giving the HS index for both species (see below the new Figure 2a,b and caption in bold).

“Figure 2 – Habitat suitability (HS) maps obtained from Bidegain et al. (2013) for *R. decussatus* (a) and *R. philippinarum* (b) in the Bay of Santander, classified into 4 HS index (HSI) classes using GIS techniques: unsuitable ($HSI < 25$), barely suitable ($25 \leq HSI < 50$), moderately suitable ($50 \leq HSI \leq 75$), highly suitable ($HSI > 75$). Spawning zones for *R. decussatus* (c) and *R. philippinarum* (d) considered in the simulations, delimited by areas with habitat suitability index values greater than 75 (i.e. highly suitable areas). Density of adult clams (>20 mm) found by Bidegain et al. (2012) in each zone following the methodology of Juanes et al. (2012) is presented in brackets. A different color is given to each spawning ground which also represents the larvae coming from each of them in Figure 6.”

In 3.3 Simulation results data, this refers to supplementary data presenting individual results of 78 simulations. The authors should come up with some useful way of presenting a summary of this data in the main manuscript. These are the key results of this manuscript, but they are never summarised and not included in the main manuscript.

We include simulations results data in the new table 2 in the main manuscript. In this new table include released particles and recruited larvae (%) for all simulations using LARVAHS and the alternative models. We eliminate the mortality column since this result can be easily deducted from the recruited percentage. Moreover we present results summarized in table 3 and the anova test conducted to compare recruitment between models.

Run	Season	Tide	Zone of release	Released (n)		Recruited LARVAHS (%)		Recruited NO BEHAVIOR (%)		Recruited NO HS (%)	
				<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>
1-37	Spring	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.036	0.144	0.009	0.027	0.461	1.027
2-38	Spring	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.009	0.011	0.001	0.002	0.282	0.639
3-39	Spring	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.062	0.036	0.019	0.000	0.690	0.804
4-40	Spring	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.215	0.460
5-41	Spring	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.005	0.015	0.006	0.030	0.191	0.628
6-42	Spring	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.004	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.234	0.384
43	Spring	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.808	–	0.410	–	1.587
7-44	Spring	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.014	0.089	0.007	0.051	0.337	0.818
8-45	Spring	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.203	0.353
9-46	Spring	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.030	0.006	0.008	0.000	0.439	0.722
10-47	Spring	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.115	0.242
11-48	Spring	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.056	0.297	0.018	0.390	0.187	0.717
12-49	Spring	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.011	0.052	0.009	0.035	0.200	0.524
50	Spring	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.676	–	0.290	–	1.514
13-51	Summer	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.222	0.687	0.029	0.350	1.480	1.623
14-52	Summer	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.034	0.200	0.026	0.230	0.994	1.225
15-53	Summer	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.089	0.064	0.021	0.074	1.219	1.319
16-54	Summer	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.024	0.051	0.021	0.220	0.914	0.909
17-55	Summer	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.015	0.536	0.766
18-56	Summer	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.009	0.052	0.013	0.080	0.722	0.908
57	Summer	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.115	–	0.360	–	1.718
19-58	Summer	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.084	0.260	0.070	0.210	0.973	1.202
20-59	Summer	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.011	0.021	0.022	0.097	0.898	0.920
21-60	Summer	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.121	0.032	0.038	0.068	1.393	1.231
22-61	Summer	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.013	0.016	0.020	0.070	0.934	0.890
23-62	Summer	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.020	0.015	0.002	0.019	0.964	0.951
24-63	Summer	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.052	0.002	0.052	0.951	0.978
64	Summer	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.006	–	0.090	–	1.746
25-65	Autumn	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.104	0.447	0.013	0.260	0.934	1.256
26-66	Autumn	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.016	0.041	0.007	0.290	0.352	0.589
27-67	Autumn	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.018	0.038	0.062	0.110	0.634	0.844
28-68	Autumn	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.308	0.643
29-69	Autumn	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.000	0.007	0.001	0.001	0.392	0.699
30-70	Autumn	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.035	0.009	0.068	0.378	0.681
71	Autumn	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.149	–	0.310	–	1.769
31-72	Autumn	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.021	0.101	0.007	0.069	0.358	0.817
32-73	Autumn	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.248	0.412
33-74	Autumn	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.038	0.040	0.010	0.002	0.809	0.790
34-75	Autumn	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.006	0.001	0.001	0.288	0.553
35-76	Autumn	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.006	0.007	0.002	0.001	0.292	0.810
36-77	Autumn	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.007	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.396	0.699
78	Autumn	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.824	–	0.190	–	1.722

“Table 2 – Predicted recruitment scores (%) for simulated *R. decussatus* (*R. dec*) and *R. philippinarum* (*R. phil.*) eggs released (= released particles x 10⁵) from each spawning zone (Astillero, Elechas, Raos, Pedreña, Cubas Outer, Cubas Inner, Solía-Tijero) in each seasonal (spring, summer and autumn) and tidal amplitude (spring or neap tides) scenario, for a total of 36 runs for *R. decussatus* (1-36, left digit in column 1) and 42 for *R. philippinarum* (37-78, right digit in column 1). Results computed by (1) LARVAHS model, (2) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS) are presented.”

Species	Recruitment succes (%)			ANOVA test				
	LARVAHS	NO BEHAVIOR	NO HS	df	SS	MS	F	p
<i>R. decussatus</i>	0.03 ±0.01 A	0.01 ±0.002 B	0.58 ±0.06 C	2	75.8	37.9	122.3	***
<i>R. philippinarum</i>	0.20 ±0.05 A	0.11 ±0.02 B	0.93 ±0.06 C	2.0	70.0	35.0	37.7	***

“Table 3 – Recruitment success (% , Mean ± SE) for *R. decussatus* (n= 36 simulations) and *R. philippinarum* (n=42) obtained using (i) the LARVAHS model, which incorporates larval behavior and habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, (ii) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and) (iii)LARVAHS model with no Habitat Suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). Results of the analysis of variance between recruitment obtained using different models are presented at right (*= p<0.05; **= p<0.001; *= p <0.0001). Tukey HSD – test results are presented by letters (A, B, C) placed after each model mean. If any two means have at least one letter in common, they are not significantly different.”**

Section 3.4 - how do you know the vertical behaviour was correctly simulated? No field data is provided to show how these bivalve larvae swim or are distributed vertically in the field.

We appreciate and agree with the comment by the reviewer regarding validation of the behavior submodel, but unfortunately we do not have data on the observed behavior. We adapted previous studies results on behavior of this genus.

At the same time, we wish to point out that in Section 3.4 Model Evaluation (now section 3.1) we evaluate the model results comparing predicted recruitment versus observed recruitment. As the reviewer suggests we cannot judge the validity of the model in terms of behavior and therefore we avoided to use the word validation and we named this section “model evaluation” since it is an evaluation or description of the results obtained by the model compared with observed data.

In any case, we agree that readers should be made aware of this issue and so we have changed the following paragraph in the discussion section and included some lines regarding model validation (see lines 715-723).

“The model predicted seasonal recruitment variability reasonably well although, like other similar models, it cannot reproduce the orders of magnitude variability since it does not include many important biological processes (e.g. specific larvae behavior, gamete fertilization success, larval mortality and growth, etc.). Thus, future analyses should be conducted upon these results by assessing the potential contribution of these parameters. Moreover, it is essential to validate the results obtained using the model through comparison with new observed data such as larvae concentration at different levels of the water column and early recruiters (< 250 microns) density.”

Text prior to and following Figure 10. Shorten substantially to one-two sentences per species.

We appreciate and agree with the comment by the reviewer 2. We also agree with reviewer 1

regarding to improve the linkage between results. In consequence we decided to rewrite, synthesized and organize 3.5, 3.6, 3.7 subsections of the original manuscript in a unique section (3.4) in order to link results about influential factors, connectivity and spawning and nursery zones (see section 3.4 or response to reviewer 1 (pp. 16-2, this document).

Shorten discussion by at least half. Unclear why information is more or less repeated as both 'Major spawning and nursery zones' and 'connectivity between spawning and nursery zones'.

We shortened the discussion section considerably (~300 words). We shortened or remove importantly repeated information mentioned by reviewer 2, but we could not shortened by a half since we added new information regarding key pieces of the study, such as model evaluation and model sensitivity to larval behavior or habitat suitability.

Figures - all figures need to have scale and direction. Figure 4 - unclear the purpose - combine a&b into one figure, and include SEs. Which species is which in figure 4b?

We agree with this comment and eliminate Figure 4b representing relationship between observed and predicted data, since it was not very informative considering the data shown are not differentiated by species. The correlation analysis results for each species were presented in text. Regarding SE, we only could present error bars for observed data since predicted data for the model and model variations were presented for analyzed data from the 78 simulations being a sum of recruited larvae coming from different spawning grounds for each season. To have variance in this results we should replicated 78 simulations (for each mode variation). Nevertheless, we repeated several simulations and the variance in recruitment was not significant.

Figure 8 - not convinced this is necessary - primary information is in Fig 7 - could this be a short table of info from Fig 8? Figure 6 - this appears to be key results but is presented far too small for a reader to see any differences.

We appreciate and agree with the first insightful comment and decided to remove figure 8 since the information presented in Figure 8 can be concluded interpreting Figure 7. The Figure 7 now is also presented as the Figure 7.

Regarding the second comment, we agree that the Figure 6 (now Figure 5) is a key result and have tested larger dots or different labels but results are less interpretable and decided to not change the figure. If the manuscript is accepted we will suggest editor to be cautious with the size of the figure in order to visualize it appropriately. Nevertheless, the colored figure (on line version) would be suitable.

While authors text is understandable, grammatical and usage errors would benefit from review by a native English speaker. As an example, the use of 'larval evolution' model is incorrect. The model has nothing to do with evolution, instead it would be more properly named as a 'larval dispersal' or 'larval behaviour' model.

The manuscript was corrected by a native English speaker as suggested by reviewer 2. Larval evolution model was substituted by larval dispersal model or the acronym LDM.

Highlights

- Larval dispersal of a native and an introduced clam species was studied.
- LARVAHS, an ENFA-based particle-tracking model was developed.
- Larval behaviour, spawning zone location, season and tides affect recruitment patterns.
- A promising approach to estimate recruitment and support fisheries management.

1 **LARVAHS: Predicting clam larval dispersal and recruitment using habitat suitability-**
2 **based particle tracking model**

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28 **Abstract**

29

30 We herein explore the potential larval dispersal and recruitment patterns of *Ruditapes*
31 *decussatus* and *Ruditapes philippinarum* clams, influenced by larval behavior and
32 hydrodynamics, by means of a particle-tracking model coupled to a hydrodynamic model. The
33 main contribution of this study is that a habitat suitability-based (ENFA, Environmental Niche
34 Factor Analysis) settlement-recruitment submodel was incorporated into the larval dispersal
35 model to simulate settlement behavior and post-settlement mortality. For this purpose, a specific
36 study was carried out in the Bay of Santander (Northern Spain), a well-mixed shallow water
37 estuary where shellfishery of both species is carried out. The model was fed with observed
38 winds, freshwater flows and astronomical tides to obtain predictions during the clams spawning
39 period. Dispersion of larvae from 7 spawning zones was tracked, subjected to three-dimensional
40 advection, vertical turbulent diffusion and imposed vertical migration behavior parameterized
41 from existing literature. Three simulation periods (Spring, Summer and Autumn) and 2 initial
42 releases (spring / neap tide) were combined in 6 different modeling scenarios. The LARVAHS
43 model proved to be a powerful approach to estimating recruitment success, highlighting the role
44 of habitat suitability, larval swimming behavior, planktonic duration, season (i.e. predominating
45 winds) and spawning ground location on recruitment success together with the effect of the tidal
46 phase at spawning. Moreover, it has proven to be a valuable tool for determining major
47 spawning and nursery grounds and to explore the connectivity between them, having important
48 implications for restoration strategies and shellfisheries as well as aquaculture management.

49

50 *Keywords: Ruditapes decussatus, Ruditapes philippinarum, larvae, particle-tracking model,*
51 *habitat suitability, ENFA, swimming behavior, recruitment, connectivity,*

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55 **1. Introduction**

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57 In intertidal and subtidal marine environments, many species are sessile or highly sedentary as
58 adults, with dispersal occurring predominantly during a planktonic larval stage (Siegel et al.,
59 2003). The supply of larvae, considered as the number of planktonic larvae available near
60 suitable settlement sites (e.g. Minchinton and Scheibling, 1991; Gaines and Bertness, 1993), is
61 the determinant of the stability of the benthic populations that depend upon the settlement and
62 recruitment of planktonic larvae to balance the adult mortality losses (e.g. Rodríguez et al.,
63 1993). Therefore, knowledge of the larval dispersal patterns between benthic habitat patches is
64 critical to understanding the connectivity and persistence of marine populations (e.g. Botsford et
65 al., 2001; Pineda et al., 2007). Thus, in recent decades, predicting the dispersion and supply of
66 larvae has been one of the major goals of population ecology (e.g. Rougharden et al., 1988),
67 especially in fisheries management and restoration activities (e.g. North et al., 2009; Savina et
68 al., 2010; Kim et al., 2012). The population dynamic of exploited species can be more sensitive
69 to recruitment dynamics, since besides weather and oceanographic conditions, larval supply is
70 linked to adult or spawning biomass, which in turn depends on the fishery (Bakun, 1996; Hsieh
71 et al. 2006).

72

73 The prediction of the larval supply needs to encompass (i) spawning stock abundance (e.g.
74 Myers, 1997; Ye, 2000), (ii) larval dispersion, which depends largely on the swimming behavior
75 of the larvae, the duration of the planktonic stage and the hydrodynamic conditions (e.g.
76 Roegner, 2000; Pineda et al. 2007) and (iii) settlement, which refers to where and when larvae
77 find a suitable habitat to metamorphose (Pineda et al. 2007; North et al., 2008). The final
78 recruitment success (i.e. the number of individuals reaching a juvenile nursery area) (North et
79 al., 2009) is influenced by the previous settlement and early post larval mortality (Hunt and
80 Scheibling, 1997).

81

82 Biophysical models integrating these factors are increasingly being used to predict larval
83 transport and explore the role of different biological and physical factors on larval dispersal and
84 settlement of marine benthic species (Metaxas and Saunders, 2009). Most of the developed
85 larval dispersal models (LDM) draw on information from hydrodynamics (i.e. water flow) and
86 simplify the larval behavior as a passive tracer (e.g. Borsa and Millet, 1992; Incze and Naimie,
87 2000; Miyake et al., 2009). They seem to be promising because they can yield detailed
88 connectivity matrices and also resolve dispersal trajectories, although they do not solve an
89 adequate level of detail in flow structures (Largier, 2003). In the last decade, important steps
90 have been made to integrate larval behavior into these models, such as age-dependent vertical
91 migration or behavioral cues (Hinckley et al. 2001; North et al., 2008; Banas et al., 2009).

92 Estuaries, lagoons and bays have proven to be excellent systems to apply these numerical
93 models in order to study the influence of biological and physical processes on larval supply.
94 These systems provide important nursery grounds and adult habitats for benthic invertebrates
95 with pelagic larval stages and their enclosed morphology, which together with the predictable
96 nature of their tidal flows and salinity variations, makes them ideal locations to easily
97 measure physical processes and larval trajectories (Thompson, 2011).

98

99 Therefore, taking into account the above mentioned aspects, the larvae of exploited benthic
100 invertebrate species in estuaries or bays should be, potentially, highly suitable to model, and the
101 results can support decision making in fisheries management, aquaculture activities and
102 conservation strategies. However, few studies have been conducted to predict larval dispersion
103 and settlement patterns of benthic commercial invertebrates' within these systems. Commercial
104 and widely distributed mollusks such as clams, oysters or abalones and crabs or fishes have
105 been the main objective species of biophysical models. Larval dispersion of these species have
106 been modeled assuming to behave as passive tracers of currents (Hinata and Tomisu, 2005;
107 Hinata and Furukawa, 2006; Stephens et al., 2006; Miyake et al., 2009), incorporating larvae
108 behavior (Herbert et al., 2012) and, in the absence of a settlement submodel, to have a

109 competent period for settlement after planktonic larval duration was completed, or over the last
110 three days of life. Recently, other authors have integrated settlement submodels in LDM and
111 assumed the presence of adult oysters (North et al., 2008) or proximity of crabs to the coast
112 (Roughan et al., 2011) as indicators of suitable zones for settlement, which by default accounted
113 for habitat suitability. Hinrichsen, et al. (2009) assumed a minimum requirement of a unique
114 environmental variable (i.e. oxygen saturation) for cod (*Gadus morhua*) settlement and
115 recruitment success.

116

117 In summary, only a few biophysical models include a habitat suitability approach in their
118 settlement subroutines, which commonly do not consider a combination of environmental
119 variables to define the suitable habitat conditions for survival of species. The subsequent aim,
120 beyond determining larval dispersal and simplified settlement patterns, is to move towards
121 including habitat suitability modeling to better understand recruitment success and post
122 settlement mortality. In this context, we developed a particle-tracking model to study the larval
123 transport, supply, and recruitment of the native clam *R. decussatus* and the introduced
124 *R. philippinarum* in the Bay of Santander (Northern Spain, Gulf of Biscay), since they require
125 taking an additional step in order to understand their recruitment patterns (Juanes et al., 2012).
126 For this purpose, the model includes a larval behavior submodel and a settlement-recruitment
127 submodel based on the habitat suitability resulting from Ecological Niche Factor Analysis
128 (ENFA), a niche-based predictive habitat suitability modelling technique for presence-only data
129 based on multivariate ordination. ENFA compares distributions of eco-geographical variables
130 between the locations where the species is present and the whole area, extracting the range of
131 environmental conditions of the locations that the species inhabits, or the niche width and
132 habitat suitability maps based on a habitat suitability index (HSI) (Hirzel, 2001; Hirzel et al.,
133 2002).

134

135 In this study we evaluate the model sensitivity to larval behavior and ENFA-based habitat
136 suitability and try to answer the questions: “Where do the larvae settle?” and “Where did the
137 settled larvae come from?” To address these two questions, the specific objectives of this study
138 are (1) investigating the effect of the location of spawning zones and hydrodynamic variables
139 (i.e. tide and wind) on larval dispersion and supply, (2) determining the most important
140 spawning zones (i.e. the major suppliers of successful recruits) and nursery grounds and (3)
141 assessing the potential connectivity between the spawning and nursery grounds.

142

143 **2. Material and methods**

144

145 **2.1. Study area**

146 This study is focused on the Bay of Santander, the largest estuary on the northern coast of Spain
147 (Gulf of Biscay) and the adjacent coast (Figure 1a). The estuary, with 22.7 km² and relatively
148 shallow waters with a mean depth of about 4.7 m, is morphologically complex and dominated
149 by intertidal areas and tidal dynamics (Galván et al., 2010). The substratum of this area varies
150 from sandy in the northern open areas to muddy sediments in the southern and inner areas
151 (Bidegain, 2013). Hydrodynamic conditions are controlled by (1) a semidiurnal tidal regime and
152 3 m of mean tidal range, interacting with variable freshwater inputs coming mainly from the
153 Miera river through the Cubas area (Puente et al., 2002) with a mean flow of 8 m³/s (Galván et
154 al., 2010) (see tidal-river currents in Figure 1b) and (2) seasonally differentiated wind currents
155 (see seasonal patterns in Figures 1c-e). In the intertidal flats, comprising 67 % of the Bay’s
156 surface, together with razor clams, the two most widely distributed commercial bivalves are the
157 native carpet shell clam (*Ruditapes decussatus*) and the introduced Manila clam (*Ruditapes
158 philippinarum*). Moreover, a Manila clam farming site covering 1 hectare is located in the
159 southeastern Elechas tidal flat. Both species’ main spawning events usually occur from Spring
160 to Autumn, according to previous studies in neighboring areas (Rodríguez-Moscoso et al.,
161 1992; Rodríguez-Moscoso and Arnaiz, 1998; Urrutia et al., 1999; Ojea et al., 2005). According

162 to the results obtained by Juanes et al. (2012) the higher recruitment intensity had occurred in
163 the central and northern zones of the Bay for the carpet shell clam and in the central and
164 innermost southern zones for the Manila clam.

165

166 **Figure 1**

167

168 **2.2. Model description**

169 The model was created by coupling a hydrodynamic model and a particle-tracking model, and
170 including behavior, disappearance, and settlement-recruitment sub-models. This latter sub-
171 model is based on the habitat suitability (HS) for the studied species, giving the LARVAHS
172 acronym to the model. The LARVAHS model calculates the movement of particles that
173 simulate larvae dynamics. In this study, it was implemented to adequately represent the larval
174 dispersal of two clam species: the native European clam (*Ruditapes decussatus*) and the
175 nonindigenous Manila clam (*Ruditapes philippinarum*). The model tracked the trajectories of
176 larvae in three dimensions and then predicted settlement and recruitment success based on
177 habitat suitability maps. The model was forced with tide, river and wind conditions which
178 occurred from April to November 2010, in order to capture a range of environmental variability
179 experienced by clam larvae during the considered spawning season. We examined whether
180 specific larval swimming behavior and seasonal and tidal conditions could influence dispersal
181 distance, encounter with suitable habitat and connectivity between grounds. The grid used in the
182 model is defined by 244 x 298 cells, each measuring 51x51 m.

183

184 **2.2.1. Hydrodynamic model**

185 Tidal current velocities were calculated by means of a two-dimensional depth-averaged
186 hydrodynamic coastal and estuarine circulation model (H2D model; see Bárcena et al., 2012a,b
187 and García et al., 2010a). This quasi three-dimensional model takes into account the different
188 structure over the depth of horizontal velocities along the depth, due to wind action (Koutitas,

189 1988). A similar implementation, i.e. the same code, same forcing data and similar domain, has
190 been previously calibrated and validated by López et al. (2013) against observed water levels,
191 current velocities and salinities, covering a full phase of spring and neap tides.

192

193 **2.2.2. Larval dispersal model: LARVAHS**

194 LARVAHS was developed from a particle-tracking model designed to predict the movement of
195 particles based on advection, sub-grid scale turbulence and larval swimming behavior.

196 Moreover, it was designed to predict larval settlement and recruitment based on previous
197 habitat-suitability raster-based maps obtained using ENFA by Bidegain et al. (2012) and
198 Bidegain (2013) in the Bay of Santander.

199

200 *Particle-tracking model*

201

202 The model uses a particle-tracking approach to simulate larval advection and diffusion.

203 Advection is computed by solving equation 1 for each particle:

204

$$205 \quad dr / dt = q \quad (1)$$

206

207 where r is the position vector of the particle and q is the current vector solved in components u
208 and v along the x and y axes. Currents are obtained by running a hydrodynamic model in
209 advance. As a consequence, the evaluation of the tidal advective transport of larvae is very fast
210 and is not limited by the Courant Friedrich Levy criterion (Kowlik & Murty, 1993). Because
211 horizontal and vertical diffusivity were constant in the hydrodynamic model, three-dimensional
212 diffusion of the turbulent particle is simulated using a random walk method (Proctor et al.,
213 1994a; Hunter, 1987; Perriñez and Elliott, 2002, Perriñez, 2004). The maximum sizes of the
214 horizontal and vertical steps, D_h and D_v respectively, are:

215

216 $D_h = \sqrt{12K_h\Delta t}$

217 $D_v = \sqrt{12K_v\Delta t}$

218

219 where K_h and K_v are the horizontal and vertical diffusion coefficients respectively. The model
220 included an external time step of 10 minutes, which is the recording time step of hydrodynamic
221 model results, and an internal time-step of 30 seconds, which is the time interval of particle
222 movement. Because of the hydrodynamic model resolution (51 m x 51 m), a given particle may
223 take several time steps to move across a grid cell. Hence the predicted currents were
224 interpolated in both space and time to provide 3D fine-resolution fields for advecting clam
225 larvae according to the hydrodynamic model outputs. For particle movement due to current
226 velocities in the x, y, and z directions, a 4th order Runge-Kutta scheme was implemented. The
227 4th order Runge-Kutta scheme provides the most robust estimate of the trajectory of particle
228 motion in water bodies with complex fronts and eddy fields (Dippner 2004) like the Bay of
229 Santander.

230

231 Regarding particle movement, different boundary conditions were imposed to the particle-
232 tracking. First, if a particle passed through the surface or bottom boundary due to turbulence or
233 vertical advection, the particle was placed back in the model domain at the previous time step
234 location. Second, if a particle passed through the surface or bottom due to swimming behavior
235 (see Behavior sub-model) it was placed just below the surface or above the bottom (i.e. it
236 stopped near the boundary). Third, if a particle intersected a horizontal boundary, it was
237 reflected off the boundary at an angle of reflection that equaled the angle of approach to the
238 boundary.

239

240 *Behavior sub-model*

241 The behavior sub-model considers the larval ability to swim vertically during its life cycle,
242 following comments and results obtained by North et al. (2006;2008), Ishii et al. (2005) Kuroda

243 (2005), and Suzuki et al (2002) for oysters such as *C. virginica* or *C. ariakensis*, or Manila
244 clam. This sub-model tries to mimic the vertical movement of larvae towards intermediate and
245 surface water layers at early stages (trochophore, D and U larvae) and to the sea-bottom, when
246 transition to pediveliger occurs. In the simulations, for the European clam, the planktonic larval
247 phase is considered for a period of 21 days (Chícharo and Chícharo, 2001b; Vela and Moreno,
248 2005). Meanwhile, for the Manila clam, the planktonic larval stage is defined for a period of 15
249 days (Young-Baek et al., 2005; Hinata and Furukawa, 2006). Table 1 summarizes the
250 behavioral considerations of the two species that were implemented into the behavior sub-
251 model.

252

253 **Table 1**

254

255 *Disappearance sub-model*

256 The disappearance sub-model associates first-order decay to each simulated particle in order to
257 reflect the egg and larval mortality induced by natural causes (predation, starvation, etc.)
258 (Morgan, 1995). We assumed egg duration of 1 day (Table 1) and a natural egg mortality of
259 99% for both species, considering that the percentage of fertilized eggs in low population
260 densities is 1% (Levitan, 1995). During the planktonic larval duration (Table 1), we assumed a
261 natural larval mortality of 98% for both species, adapting results obtained by several authors
262 (e.g. Carriker, 1961; Chícharo and Chícharo, 2001b; Zhang and Yan 2006).

263

$$264 \quad dN/dt = -kN$$

265

266 where N is the number of eggs released, t is the specific life cycle duration (see Table 1) in
267 seconds and k is the considered egg or larval mortality rate (s^{-1}) to obtain the assumed natural
268 mortality percentages.

269

270 *Settlement-recruitment sub-model*

271 We used a habitat-suitability (HS) raster-based grid to determine if a pediveliger-stage larvae
272 encountered a suitable habitat to settle and recruit. Each cell of the grid had a HS index (HSI)
273 which ranged from 0 to 100, with higher values being more suitable for recruitment and zero
274 being completely unsuitable. This grid was obtained from the ecological niche factor analysis
275 (ENFA) conducted by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) for each of the studied
276 species in the Bay of Santander obtaining reasonably good model validation results (see Figure
277 2a). Different topographic (depth), physical (salinity, current velocity and sediment
278 characteristics such as percentage of sand, gravel and silt) and chemical environmental variables
279 (organic matter content in sediment), assumed as meaningful to the ecology and distribution of
280 these species (e.g. Laing and Child, 1996; Vincenzi et al., 2006, Cannas, 2010) were considered,
281 together with presence data to perform this analysis. The integration of habitat suitability grids
282 in the model grid was automatic since the extent of the study area and the cell size used were
283 identical.

284

285 The minimum HSI value considered for recruitment to occur was 25, assuming a HSI value
286 from 0 to 25 to be an unsuitable habitat for recruitment (see Figure 2a,b). For every internal
287 time step (30 s), each pediveliger-stage particle was tested to determine if it was at the sea-
288 bottom. When it was at the bottom, the sub-model checked if the HSI on this cell was greater
289 than 25 and in that case, the particle settled, or stopped moving. When the HSI was lower than
290 25, the particle continued swimming. Finally, if the particle did not encounter a cell of HSI > 25
291 at the end of the pediveliger-stage, the particle dies.

292

293 Once a given particle settled in a cell, the HSI value of this cell was assumed as the survival
294 probability of the particle. To perform the larval recruitment, the model generated a random
295 number between 0 and 100. If this random number was lower than the survival probability of
296 the particle (the HSI), the settled particle survived and it was successfully recruited. On the

297 contrary, if the random number was greater than the survival probability of the particle, the
298 settled particle died.

299

300 **2.3. Initial conditions and scenarios**

301

302 **2.3.1. Spawning zones**

303 Initial conditions for the simulations were defined for the major spawning areas in the Bay of
304 Santander. Spawning areas were considered those defined as highly suitable ($HSI > 75$) for both
305 species by Bidegain et al. (2012) and Bidegain (2013) using ENFA (see Figures 2a,b), assuming
306 a higher density and reproductive efficiency of adults in these areas. Thus, using this criterion
307 we determined 6 spawning grounds for *R. decussatus* and 7 for *R. philippinaurum* (Figures 2c,d).

308

309 **Figure 2**

310

311 **2.3.2. Number of particles (eggs) released**

312 The number of particles released in each spawning zone and scenario was proportional to the
313 density of female adult clams and the area of the spawning ground. It was calculated by
314 multiplying (1) $\frac{1}{2}$ of adult density (individuals/m²) in the spawning ground considering a 1:1
315 male/female ratio by (2) the number of cells within the area, and (3) the area of each cell (51 x
316 51 m) and (4) the number of eggs produced by each female adult clam. Considering previous
317 estimations of the broodstock conditioning of this species (Yap, 1977; Chung et al., 2001; Park
318 and Choi, 2004; Matías et al., 2009) we assumed a total of 0.6×10^6 eggs released by each
319 female clam for both species (i.e. 100,000 in each scenario). A maximum of ~1 million particles
320 were released from the most productive spawning zone due to computational constraints.
321 Therefore, each released particle represented 1×10^5 eggs, in order to achieve the assumed egg
322 production per female. Note that in Elechas, for the two cells where the Manila clam farming

323 area is located (1 hectare), a density of 100 adult clams/m² was assumed (Data provided by the
324 Regional Fisheries Administration).

325

326 **2.3.3. Simulation scenarios and environmental conditions**

327 Three spawning seasons were tested within the identified spawning period for both species
328 (April-November, Rodriguez-Moscoso et al., 1992; Rodríguez-Moscoso and Arnaiz, 1998;
329 Urrutia et al., 1999; Ojea et al., 2005): Spring, Summer and Autumn 2010. In each season two
330 egg releases were tested: 15/04 and 25/04 (Spring), 12/08 and 20/08 (Summer), and 09/10 and
331 16/10 (Autumn) in 2010. The first date of release in each season coincided with neap tide and
332 the second one with spring tide. Tidal-river and wind currents during simulation periods are
333 presented in Figure 1. The seawater circulation pattern due to tidal and river forcing is presented
334 as mean annual currents (Figure 1b) considering that the tidal force is similar for all seasons and
335 river outputs were low in general (< 2 m³/s) and not significantly different between seasons
336 (Bidegain et al., 2013). Regarding winds, each season was mainly characterized by a
337 predominating wind: SW winds in Spring, NE winds in Summer and W winds in Autumn,
338 resulting in northward/offshore (Figure 1c), southward/inshore (Figure 1d) and eastward wind
339 currents (Figure 1e) respectively. Thus, 6 scenarios were tested from each spawning zone and
340 species, corresponding to different tidal phases and seasons.

341

342 **2.4. LARVAHS model evaluation**

343 A preliminary evaluation of the LARVAHS model to predict recruitment of clams was
344 conducted in two nursery grounds (Elechas and Raos) by comparing predictions with observed
345 data. Moreover, two variations of this model were also evaluated in order to analyze the role of
346 larval behavior and habitat suitability in recruitment: (1) a LARVAHS model with no behavior
347 submodel (NO BEHAVIOR model) and (2) a LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability
348 based recruitment submodel, obtaining settled larvae (NO HS model). The evaluation grounds
349 were selected because (i) they are located near each other and thus allows for the sampling of

350 both grounds during the same tide and (ii) shellfishing activity is minimal since they are located
351 far from the coastline or out of the permitted shellfishing zones. Hence, the potential mortality
352 of early recruiters associated with this activity (raking or pressing the sediment) was minimal.

353

354 Predicted densities were compared with observed densities of early recruiters and the strength of
355 the correlation was analyzed by Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. Predicted recruitment
356 density was calculated by dividing the number of individuals successfully recruited in each
357 nursery ground at each season (adding larvae coming from different spawning grounds at both
358 tidal scenarios) by the nursery ground area. To obtain the observed early recruiters density, four
359 sediment samples of 50 cm² to a depth of 15 cm were collected in each nursery ground on the
360 29th of June, the 23rd of October and the 12th of December, i.e. after each spawning season
361 modeled in the study (Spring, Summer, Autumn). All samples were passed through a 1 mm
362 sieve and clam lengths were measured to the nearest 0.1 mm. Individuals larger than 1 mm but
363 smaller than 3 mm for *R. decussatus* and 5 mm for *R. philippinarum* were considered as early
364 recruiters. This selection criterion was based on differential growth patterns described for these
365 clam species (Arnal and Fernández-Pato, 1977, 1978; Spencer et al., 1991; Solidoro et al., 2000;
366 Chessa et al., 2005) as well as the desire to avoid counting early recruiters of the previous
367 spawning season.

368

369 **2.5. Data analysis**

370

371 **2.5.1. Simulation results and model sensitivity**

372 For each spawning zone in each tidal and seasonal scenario the percentage of the total eggs
373 released which resulted in successfully recruited clams was calculated for *R. decussatus* and *R.*
374 *philippinarum* by running simulations using the LARVAHS, the NO BEHAVIOR model and
375 the NO HS model. Normality and homogeneity of variance were examined by Shapiro-Wilk
376 and Levene tests, respectively, and data were transformed if these assumptions for a parametric

377 analysis were violated. An ANOVA- test and post-hoc Tukey's HSD –test were applied to the
378 recruitment data to find out if differences exist between the model results and to examine the
379 model sensitivity to larval behavior and habitat suitability incorporation. A t-test was also
380 performed to determine if recruitment success was significantly different between species for
381 each variation of the model.

382

383 **2.5.2. Influential factors on recruitment success**

384 Recruitment success, calculated as the percentage of the total eggs released that were retained
385 in the Bay and successfully recruited, was used as a response variable to compare the results
386 obtained from different runs. A t-test was performed to determine if recruitment success was
387 significantly different between the studied species with differing larval phase durations. In
388 addition, to analyze the single and interactive effects of the location of the spawning site, the
389 tidal amplitude and the season on recruitment success, a multifactorial ANOVA was conducted.

390

391 **2.5.3. Determination of major spawning and nursery grounds**

392 We calculated, for the eggs released in each spawning ground (i.e. HSI > 75), the proportion of
393 larvae recruited in the whole Bay (i.e. HSI >25) and defined as the most successful spawning
394 grounds those from where, after larval release and dispersal, the highest total recruitments or
395 percentages were obtained.

396

397 Delimitation of nursery grounds by cells HSI > 25 (i.e. where recruitment occurs in the model)
398 was not viable if we were to analyze recruitment spatial patterns, since most of the nursery
399 grounds overlapped using this criterion (see Figures 2a,b). Therefore, we decided to consider the
400 nursery grounds as being identical to the spawning grounds (i.e. highly suitable areas, HSI > 75)
401 in order to have them clearly separated from each other, facilitating the analysis and
402 interpretation of results regarding the determination of major nursery grounds and/or
403 connectivity between grounds. To determine major nursery grounds, recruitment density was

404 calculated in each ground by adding together larvae coming from different spawning grounds at
405 different tidal and seasonal scenarios and dividing the number of individuals by the nursery
406 ground area (= spawning ground area).

407

408 **2.5.4. Connectivity between spawning and nursery grounds**

409 Connectivity matrices were created for each spawning season and tidal scenario. The
410 connectivity matrices, adapted from Savina et al. (2010) indicate which proportion of the total
411 larvae recruited in a given nursery zone (x-axis) comes from each spawning zone (y-axis).
412 Attending these proportions, the robustness between spawning and nursery grounds connections
413 and the isolation and self-recruitment of grounds was analyzed.

414

415 **3. Results**

416

417 **3.1. LARVAHS model evaluation**

418 The LARVAHS model estimations were evaluated in two zones (Raos and Elechas) and for the
419 three studied seasons (Spring, Summer, Autumn) revealing that the predicted recruitment
420 density values were lower than the mean observed values in general, for both species and all
421 seasons (see black circles in Figure 3), except in the summer scenario in Raos. The generalized
422 underestimation of the LARVAHS model was not significantly different between species
423 considering that when underestimation occurred it was $3.62 (\pm 1.47) (\pm SD)$ individuals/m² for
424 *R. decussatus* (Figures 3a,b) and $3.28 (\pm 2.09)$ individuals/m² for *R. philippinarum* (Figures
425 3c,d). Figure 3 shows that the seasonal variability in recruitment patterns was detected by the
426 LARVAHS model, obtaining significant correlation values between observed and predicted
427 recruitment density for *R. decussatus* (Spearman's $R=0.89$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 4.1$, $p=0.0$) and *R.*
428 *philippinarum* (Spearman's $R=0.94$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 5.6$, $p=0.005$) which involves a good
429 qualitative fit of the model to the in situ measured data.

430

431 However, seasonal variability in recruitment was not detected by the two variations of the
432 LARVAHS model and the correlation values obtained between predictions and observed data
433 were not significant, neither for the NO BEHAVIOR model (*R. philippinarum*, $R=0.07$, $n=6$, t
434 $(n-2) = 0.14$, $p=0.89$; *R. philippinarum*, $R=0.70$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 1.94$, $p=0.12$), nor for the NO
435 HS model (*R. philippinarum*, $R=0.46$, $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 1.05$, $p=0.35$; *R. philippinarum*, $R=0.430$,
436 $n=6$, $t(n-2) = 0.95$, $p=0.40$). Moreover, the NO BEHAVIOR model results underestimated the
437 observed data more significantly than the LARVHAS model in all cases for both species, and
438 using the NO HS model the overestimation was highly appreciable (Figure 3).

439

440 **Figure 3**

441

442 **3.2. Simulation results data and model sensitivity**

443 Results of the 78 runs, 36 runs for *R. decussatus* and 42 runs for *R. philippinarum* are presented
444 in Table 2 for the LARVAHS model and the two described variations of this model: the
445 LARVAHS model without the behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and the LARVAHS
446 model without the habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). For each spawning
447 zone the particles released were different, according to the zone extension and the density of
448 adults clams. Thus, for *R. decussatus* Cubas the Outer ground, with $\sim 800000 \times 10^5$ eggs
449 released, was the most “egg productive” spawning zone, followed by Astillero and Pedreña with
450 $\sim 188000 \times 10^5$ and $\sim 164000 \times 10^5$ eggs released, respectively. Additionally, the Pedreña
451 spawning zone, with 963000×10^5 eggs released was the most productive zone for *R.*
452 *philippinarum*, followed by Elechas with $\sim 333000 \times 10^5$ eggs released.

453

454 **Table 2**

455

456 The recruitment percentages were very low for the LARVAHS model and also for the two
457 variations of the model, due mainly to high natural mortality rates and low retention of larvae

458 within the Bay, or to settlement in unsuitable zones. Recruitment success was significantly
459 higher for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus* (see Table 3) for LARVAHS (df=76, t=-3.38,
460 p=0.001) and also for the two model variations (No Behavior, df= 76, t=-2.45, p=0.01; No HS,
461 df= 76, t=-4.48, p=0.0003). The analysis of the variance of recruitment success between models
462 showed significant differences between all of the models for both species, with the significantly
463 highest recruitment for the NO HS model and the lowest recruitment percentages for the NO
464 BEHAVIOR model (Table 3).

465

466 **Table 3**

467

468 **3.3. Larval dynamics**

469 The assumed vertical behavior of *R. decussatus* and *R. philippinarum* larvae adapted from
470 literature (see Table 1) was correctly simulated (see Figure 4 and Video S1, supplementary
471 information). During the trocophore phase, we found all larvae at the surface (Figure 4a) while
472 D and early Umbo-stage larvae were found at surface to intermediate depths (Figure 4b). Late
473 Umbo and early Pediveliger-stage larvae were found uniformly distributed at all depths (Figure
474 4c), while late Pediveliger larvae were observed close to the bottom (Figure 4d). Regarding
475 spatial dynamics, Video S2 (see supplementary information) helps to visualize larval pool
476 movements and shows the plume of larvae alternatively flushed in and out of the Bay with the
477 tidal currents, and a differentiated retention of larvae depending on the zone of spawning.
478 Nevertheless, final recruitment spatial patterns occurring after larval dispersal and influential
479 factors are described in later sections.

480

481 **Figure 4**

482

483

484

485 **3.4. Influential factors on recruitment and connectivity between grounds**

486 Recruitment data (i.e., the percentage of the total released eggs successfully recruited) were first
487 log-transformed to achieve normality and homogeneity of variance. The factorial ANOVA
488 results presented in Table 4 shows that season (i.e. predominating winds) and the location of the
489 spawning zone have significant effects on the final recruitment success of both clam species.
490 The location of spawning zone contributed more importantly to the overall variance.
491 Additionally, the tidal phase (spring or neap) at the spawning moment had no significant effect
492 on the recruitment of either of the two species. However, the interaction between these two
493 factors had a significant effect for *R. decussatus* (Table 4) and a tidal effect on connection
494 patterns between spawning and nursery grounds can be appreciated (Figure 8).

495

496 **Table 4**

497

498 *Season and winds*

499 Regarding spawning season, the highest recruitments of both species' larvae were observed in
500 summer, with predominating NE winds (Figure 1d) which aided the retention of larvae in the
501 western and southern flats of the Bay (Figures 5b,e). These wind currents in summer also helped
502 to generate more frequent connections between the northwestern spawning grounds and the
503 southwestern nursery grounds (Figure 6). Regarding these connections between grounds, the
504 most robust ones (i.e. more than 30 % of the total larvae recruited in a given nursery ground
505 originating from a given spawning site, green and black rectangles) occurred more frequently
506 for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus* and particularly in summer at neap tides.
507 Conversely, a limited recruitment was observed in spring (northward currents) (Figures 5a,d)
508 and in Autumn (eastward currents) (Figures 5c,f) corresponding to weaker connections between
509 grounds, particularly at spring tides (Figure 6).

510

511 **Figure 5**

512 **Figure 6**

513

514 *Spawning zones*

515 Regarding zones, for *R. decussatus* larvae released from the western and southern zones of the
516 Bay, Raos and Astillero respectively, showed the highest proportions of recruited individuals,
517 particularly in summer (Figure 7a). This higher retention within the Bay when spawning occurs
518 in southern zones is demonstrated in Video S2 (see supplementary information) as mentioned
519 above. Moreover, although Cubas Outer, in the north, was not a very successful spawning
520 ground it was significant in terms of absolute values of larvae recruited, owing to the high
521 number of eggs released (Table 2). For this species, the interaction between the spawning zone
522 and tides was significant. Thus, for instance, when eggs were released in Cubas Outer, the final
523 recruitment was significantly higher at spring tide than at neap tide, while when spawning
524 occurred in southern zones (Astillero or Elechas) recruitment was higher at neap tide than at
525 spring tide (Table 2). For *R. philippinarum*, larvae released from the southern Bay (Astillero and
526 Solía-Tijero) showed the highest recruitment rates (Figure 7b) and these were also the major
527 spawning grounds in terms of the number of individuals recruited. Moreover, this species
528 showed similar patterns regarding tide-zone effect (although not statistically significant) (Table
529 2 and Table 4), together with a significantly higher number and the most robust connections,
530 which occurred at neap tides (Figure 6).

531

532 **Figure 7**

533

534 *Major nursery grounds and connectivity with spawning grounds*

535 The predicted major current nursery grounds in the Bay of Santander were (1) Cubas Outer in
536 the northeastern grounds of the estuary with ~ 80 recruiters/m² and Raos (17 recruiters/m²) in the
537 central western flats for *R. decussatus* and (2) Solía-Tijero in the southern inner zones of the
538 Bay (240 recruiters/m²) and Cubas Outer in the northeastern area of the bay and Astillero

539 grounds with 50 and 40 recruiters/m², respectively, for *R. philippinarum* (Figure 8). The
540 predicted recruitment density for the whole Bay in highly suitable areas (i.e. the sum of
541 individuals recruited in cells with habitat suitability index (HSI) >75 divided by the total area
542 of the nursery grounds) was considerably higher for *R. philippinarum* with 50 recruiters/m²
543 than for *R. decussatus* with 17 recruiters/m², as a result of a higher retention of larvae within the
544 Bay and a smaller area of highly suitable habitat for recruitment for *R. philippinarum* (317
545 Hectares) compared with *R. decussatus* (407 Hectares) (see Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013).

546

547 **Figure 8**

548

549 Regarding the most important nursery grounds estimated in this study (Figure 8), for *R.*
550 *decussatus* Cubas Outer nursery ground can be considered a self-recruitment ground in spring at
551 spring tide, while it received “allochthonous” larvae from Cubas Inner in this season at neap
552 tides and also in Autumn at spring tides (Figure 6a). Additionally, Raos also exhibited self-
553 recruitment behavior, except in Summer and Autumn at neap tide. For *R. philippinarum*, Solía-
554 Tijero and Astillero displayed self-recruitment behavior although they received recruiters from
555 several zones, particularly at neap tide when retention within the Bay is higher (Figure 6b).
556 Also, for this species, Cubas Outer received significant amounts of larvae coming from Cubas
557 Inner and Elechas in Summer and Autumn. Finally, the most isolated nursery was Cubas Inner
558 for both species, considering that it did not recruit larvae from any of the spawning sites.

559

560 **4. Discussion**

561

562 The incorporation of habitat suitability modelling results obtained by ENFA has proven to be a
563 powerful approach to creating larval dispersal models (LDM) with cues which stimulate larval
564 settlement and including an estimator of recruitment success (Turner et al. 1994, Tamburri et al.
565 1996). This advance follows the recommendations, of the relevant ICES working group, to

566 couple LDM with additional spatial information in order to delineate the source populations, as
567 well as the recruitment habitat, along the path of an individual particle (North et al., 2009).
568 The LARVAHS model, incorporating habitat suitability as well as swimming behavior, was
569 reasonably suitable in its ability to qualitatively forecast seasonal variability of recruitment, and
570 the obtained predictions significantly correlated with observed data (Figure 3). Moreover,
571 estimated spatial recruitment patterns considerably agree with those found in this estuary by
572 Juanes et al. (2012), finding higher densities in northern open zones for *R. decussatus* and in
573 southern inner zones for *R. philippinarum*.

574

575 *Swimming behavior and habitat suitability*

576 In order to analyze the role of swimming behavior and habitat suitability submodels in
577 recruitment predictions we considered it necessary to compare estimations obtained by the
578 LARVAHS model with those obtained by two variations of the model (i.e. a NO HS model,
579 using settled larvae without a habitat suitability- recruitment submodel and (ii) a NO
580 BEHAVIOR model, a passive behavior model that ignores swimming ability. This
581 comparative analysis showed that these two variations of the LARVAHS model did not
582 adequately forecast seasonal patterns and no significant correlations were observed with field
583 data. On one hand, the absence of habitat suitability led to a strong overestimation of
584 recruitment, since the important post settlement mortality associated with recruitment of benthic
585 invertebrates (Hunt and Scheibling, 1997) was not integrated in the NO HS model and,
586 consequently, all larvae settled within the Bay survived. On the other hand, the NO
587 BEHAVIOR model with a passive behavior of larvae underestimated the observed recruitment
588 more significantly than the LARVAHS model. This result suggests that the incorporation of
589 swimming behavior favored larvae retention within the Bay, influencing their encounter with a
590 suitable habitat for recruitment (Table 3). According to Kuroda (2005), this vertical-down
591 "migration" is essential to prevent all larvae from being dragged into offshore areas at ebb tide.
592 This finding is consistent with recent observations by Herbert et al. (2012) for *R. philippinarum*,

593 and such vertical swimming behavior also has a major impact on the distribution in tidal
594 estuaries of other species which broadcast larvae, such as crustaceans (Zeng and Naylor, 1996)
595 and other bivalves (North et al., 2008).

596

597 Regarding specific differences, recruitment of larvae within the Bay was significantly higher for
598 *R. philippinarum* with all the models (Table 3). In the case of the LARVAHS model, this
599 outcome was remarkable, since we considered larger areas of suitable habitat for recruitment of
600 *R. decussatus* compared with *R. philippinarum* (see Figure 2 and Bidegain, 2013). This suggests
601 that retention of larvae might be a more critical determinant of final recruitment than the
602 difference in suitable habitat surface area between species. When we modeled larvae dispersal
603 without incorporating habitat suitability, the differences in recruitment between species were
604 more significant (i.e. higher t-statistic values) than for the LARVAHS or NO BEHAVIOR
605 models, suggesting that specific differences in post larval mortality associated with differences
606 in highly suitable surface areas has a stronger effect on recruitment than specific differences in
607 planktonic larval duration (PLD) (or each larval phase duration).

608

609 *Planktonic larval duration*

610 Results obtained with the NO BEHAVIOR (or passive swimming) model showed that the PLD
611 had an effect on larvae retention and final recruitment within the estuary. A longer PLD of *R.*
612 *decussatus* has a significant negative effect on larval retention, resulting in higher mortality
613 rates and lower recruitment success than *R. philippinarum*. Thus, the longer PLD of *R.*
614 *decussatus* over *R. philippinarum* seems to be the main reason for the higher larval dispersion
615 and lower recruitment rates for this species. This result is consistent with the outcomes of the
616 few biophysical models that have tested for it and found significant effects of PDL on larval
617 transport (Edwards et al., 2007). For example, increasing the PLD significantly of brittle star
618 (echinoderms) decreases the larval retention in the natal region and increases the larval

619 mortality (Lefebvre et al., 2003). Moreover, a reduction in the PDL of scallop larvae decreases
620 their displacement distance (Tremblay et al., 1994).

621

622 *Season, spawning ground location and tidal effect*

623 The results suggest that the location of the source populations and wind-induced currents have
624 significant effects on the recruitment of both species (Table 4). The complex configuration of
625 the Bay of Santander with both inner/narrower areas and more open tidal flats, where spawning
626 grounds are located, appears to have the greatest impact on the success of larval retention and
627 recruitment, explaining ~60-70 % of the total variance of recruitment. Herbert et al. (2012)
628 found similar results when modelling *R. philippinarum* larval transport in Pool Harbour
629 (England) which contains different embayments. Hinckley et al. (2001) highlighted the
630 importance of spawning location and timing to successful walleye pollock *Theragra*
631 *chalcogramma* larval transport to nursery areas. Moreover, Rigal et al. (2010) demonstrated that
632 the interaction between spawning location and hydrodynamics have important effects on
633 retention of the gastropod *Crepidula fornicata* within a coastal bay. Wind advection has been
634 considered to have important effects in larval distribution in large (~1000 km²) and vertically
635 stratified bays (Hinata and Tomisu, 2005) and open coastal areas (e.g. Bas et al., 2009; Ayata et
636 al., 2010) where wind-induced currents are usually important together with water movements
637 due to tides. Therefore, although initially it may be assumed that in a small estuary like the Bay
638 of Santander this wind effect would not be important, our results suggest that wind-induced
639 hydrodynamics is a factor to be considered, being responsible for the ~ 8 – 14 % of the total
640 variance of recruitment. Other studies have also shown that wind effects are important in larval
641 distribution (Suzuki et al., 2002; Leis, 2006; Ayata et al., 2010) and under some conditions the
642 wind-induced physical structure could be an important mechanism of retention of invertebrate
643 larvae (Epifanio et al., 1989; Verdier-Bonnet et al., 1997).

644 The interaction between spawning zone location and tidal phase at the spawning moment
645 showed an effect on final recruitment, being statistically significant for *R. decussatus* and

646 explaining 22 % of the total variance. Recruitment was higher at spring tides in the outer zone
647 of Cubas, probably due to the return of larvae to the mouth of estuary helped by tides, and
648 higher at neap tides in the inner southern zones since neap tides limited flushing larvae out of
649 estuary. Similarly, recruitment of larvae retention of crabs or clam larvae is higher when
650 spawning occurs at neap tides than at spring tides (Forward, 1987, Gove and Paula, 2000;
651 Chícharo and Chícharo, 2000:2001a) and the ingress of crab larvae in a estuary and settlement is
652 higher at times, ranging from several days after spring tide to near the neap tide (Roegner et al.,
653 2007).

654

655 *Major spawning and nursery zones*

656 The models ability to identify major spawning and nursery grounds could support shellfishery
657 management strategies such as restoration, cultivation and creation of “sanctuaries” or protected
658 areas, with the potential of supplementing populations outside the protected area both under
659 normal conditions and in the cases of unforeseen events or decline of populations (Allison et al.,
660 1998; Peterson, 2002; Jones, 2006). However, the results obtained in this study should be taken
661 with caution since the selection of a high HSI threshold (i.e. 75) to define spawning or nursery
662 grounds is a simplification of the reality in easily delimited grounds, adopted in order to avoid
663 overlapping and facilitate interpretation and analysis of results. Lower thresholds may lead to
664 larger grounds but with lower estimations of average spawner adult densities or recruitment
665 rates. Therefore, depending on the management needs, a combination of detection of the main
666 hot spot(s), delimitation of larger sanctuaries and interpretability of results should be considered
667 in order to select the appropriate HSI threshold.

668

669 Therefore, suitable sites for the application of these strategies for the native clam *R. decussatus*
670 could be located in successful spawning zones in terms of final recruitment. However, for the
671 introduced clam *R. philippinarum* sanctuaries should be located in grounds where dramatic
672 retentions of larvae and widespread proliferation or domination would not occur. For this

673 species, less successful spawning zones could be considered. In this regard, the limited
674 proliferation and no general domination patterns of the nonindigenous clam may be related to
675 the suitable location of this species cultivation zone in the not especially-successful spawning
676 ground of Elechas (Figure 7).

677

678 The major nursery zones in the Bay of Santander, regarding the predicted recruitment density of
679 larvae, were Solía-Tijero for *R. philippinarum* and Cubas Outer for *R. decussatus*. These
680 predicted major nursery zones partially coincided with the density of adult clams (Figure 2) or
681 the recruitment patterns estimated by Juanes et al. (2012). Non-coincidences can be easily
682 explained by (1) the temporal recruitment variability, (2) the fact that the recruitment density
683 was predicted only in highly suitable areas and (3) other factors which significantly influence
684 the final density of adults not integrated in the habitat suitability model such as the differential
685 predation occurring between recruitment zones. This last hypothesis is consistent with the high
686 predation of clams by crabs and fishes found in the Bay (Bidegain and Juanes, 2013). Seasonal
687 protection regimes for estimated major nursery zones could be also efficient supplements to
688 more traditional fishery management practices.

689

690 *Connectivity between spawning and nursery grounds*

691 The model also provided theoretical outcomes concerning connectivity between grounds. Our
692 results suggest that there are both isolated areas or “self-recruitment nursery grounds” and areas
693 that are potentially well connected, where recruited larvae come from distant or nearby
694 spawning grounds in several scenarios. In general, a considerably higher number of
695 connections was observed for *R. philippinarum* than for *R. decussatus*. The shorter PLD and
696 higher retention of *R. philippinarum* larvae may be one of the main reasons which explains this
697 difference between species. In the same line, it seems that neap tides and dominating NE winds
698 of summer favored connections between grounds, particularly for *R. philippinarum*. The
699 connectivity between internal areas of the south with northern distant areas was less evident

700 than between non distant zones or nearby inner grounds, being consistent with the fact that
701 retention of larvae in inner nearby grounds is higher and connections between them could be
702 more easily produced.

703

704 Overall, more self-recruitment cases were found for *R. decussatus* which is, consequently, the
705 species with lower potential recruitment success. Self-recruitment nursery grounds, which
706 notably do not receive larvae from other grounds, are more susceptible to recruitment declines
707 when scenarios favoring the export of larvae from this given ground out of the Bay occur.
708 Whereas well connected areas can compensate for the larvae deficit coming from a given
709 spawning site with larvae pools from other sources.

710

711 **5. Conclusions**

712

713 The LARVAHS model may serve as a useful framework to guide quantitative investigations
714 about settlement and recruitment predictions since it has an important focus in habitat suitability
715 modelling-based recruitment estimations. The model predicted seasonal recruitment variability
716 reasonably well although, like other similar models, it cannot reproduce the orders of magnitude
717 variability since it does not include many important biological processes (e.g. specific larvae
718 behavior, gamete fertilization success, larval mortality and growth, post-settlement mortality
719 due to predation, etc.). Thus, future analyses should be conducted upon these results by
720 assessing the potential contribution of these parameters. Moreover, it is essential to validate the
721 results obtained using the model through comparison with new observed data such as larvae
722 concentration at different levels of the water column and early recruiters (< 250 microns)
723 density.

724

725 Model results have implications for shellfisheries and aquaculture management and also
726 conservation programs. However, grid resolution constrains the applicability of predictions and,

727 consequently, refined circulation predictions may be necessary to better guide the location of
728 specific management and conservation strategies.

729

730 **Acknowledgements**

731

732 The work described in this paper was partially supported by the Department of Livestock,
733 Agriculture and Fisheries from the Regional Government of Cantabria, through the Regional
734 Fisheries and Food Administration and by the VI National Plan (2008-2011) for Research in
735 Science & Technological Innovation of the Spanish Government (Project CGL2009-10620). We
736 wish to thank the shell-fishermen, technicians and inspectors of the Fisheries Service who
737 collaborated in the acquisition of data. We are grateful to Giovanni Coco for helpful comments
738 and recommendations. This paper constitutes part of Gorka Bidegain's PhD thesis.

739

740 **References**

741

742 Allison, G.W., Lubchenco, J., Carr, M.H., 1998. Marine Reserves are Necessary but not
743 Sufficient for Marine Conservation. *Ecological Applications* 8 (1), S79-S92

744

745 Arnal, J.I., Fernández-Pato, C., 1977. La croissance de la palourde, *Venerupis decussatus* L., a
746 la Baie de Santander (Espagne): premières resultats. *Int. Counc. Exp. Sea CM* 1977/K, 16.

747

748 Arnal, J.I., Fernández-Pato, C., 1978. La croissance de la palourde, *Venerupis decussatus* L., a
749 la Baie de Santander (Espagne) dans des conditions naturelles. *Int. Counc. Exp. Sea CM*
750 1978/K, 28.

751

752 Ayata, S.-D., Lazure, P., Thiébaud, É., 2010. How does the connectivity between populations
753 mediate range limits of marine invertebrates? A case study of larval dispersal between the Bay
754 of Biscay and the English Channel (northeast- Atlantic). *Progress in Oceanography* 87, 18–36.
755

756 Bakun, A., 1996. *Patterns in the Ocean: Ocean Processes and Marine Population Dynamics*.
757 University of California Sea Grant, San Diego, California, USA, in cooperation with Centro de
758 Investigaciones Biológicas de Noroeste, La Paz, Baja California Sur, Mexico. 323 pp.
759

760 Banas, N.S., McDonald, S.P., Armstrong, D.A., 2009. Green crab larval retention in Willapa
761 Bay, Washington. An intensive Lagrangian modeling approach. *Estuaries Coasts* 32, 893–905.
762

763 Bárcena, J.F., Garcia, A., Gómez, A.G., Alvarez, C., Juanes, J.A., Revilla, J.A., 2012a. Spatial
764 and temporal flushing time approach in estuaries influenced by river and tide. An application in
765 Suances Estuary (Northern Spain). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 112, 40-51.
766

767 Bárcena, J.F., García, A., García, J., Álvarez, C. , Revilla, J.A., 2012b. Surface analysis of free
768 surface and velocity to changes in river flow and tidal amplitude on a shallow mesotidal estuary:
769 An application in Suances Estuary (Northern Spain). *Journal of Hydrology* 14, 301-318.
770

771 Bas C., Luppi T., Spivak E., Schejter L., 2009. Larval dispersion of the estuarine crab *Neohelice*
772 *granulata* in coastal marine waters of the Southwest Atlantic. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf*
773 *Science* 83, 569-576.
774

775 Bidegain, G., 2013. Ecological dynamics of a native and an introduced clam species:
776 Implications for conservation and fisheries management. PhD thesis. University of Cantabria.
777 306 pp.

778

779 Bidegain, G., Juanes, J.A., 2013. Does expansion of Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* cause
780 competitive displacement of the European native clam *Ruditapes decussatus*? Journal of
781 Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 445. 44-52.

782

783 Borsa, P., Millet, B., 1992. Recruitment of the clam *Ruditapes decussatus* Estuarine, Coastal
784 and Shelf Science, 35: 289-300.

785

786 Botsford, L., Hastings, A., Gaines, S.D., 2001. Dependence of sustainability on the
787 configuration of marine reserves and larval dispersal distance. Ecology Letters 4, 144–150.

788

789 Cannas, A., 2010. Population dynamics of *Ruditapes decussatus* (L.) and settlement of
790 *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve) in Sardinia, Italy. PhD Thesis. University of
791 Cagliari.

792

793 Carriker, M. R., 1961. Interrelation of functional morphology, behaviour, and autecology in
794 early stages of the bivalve *Mercenaria mercenaria*. J. Elisha Mitchell scient Soc. 77, 168-241.

795

796 Chessa, L.A., Paesanti, F., Pais, A., Scardi, M., Serra, S., Vitale, L., 2005. Perspective for
797 development of low impact aquaculture in western Mediterranean lagoon: the case of the carpet
798 clam *Tapes decussatus*. Aquacult. Int. 13, 147-155.

799

800 Chícharo, L. & M. A. Chícharo (2000). Short-term fluctuations in bivalve larvae compared with
801 some environmental factors in a coastal lagoon (South Portugal). Scientia marina 64 (4), 1-8.

802

803 Chícharo, L., Chícharo, M.A., 2001a. Effects of environmental conditions on planktonic
804 abundances, benthic recruitment and growth rates of the bivalve mollusc *Ruditapes decussates*
805 in a Portuguese coastal lagoon. *Fish Res* 53, 235–250.
806

807 Chícharo, L., Chícharo, M.A., 2001b. A Juvenile Recruitment Prediction Model for *Ruditapes*
808 *decussatus* (L.) (Bivalvia: Mollusca). *Fisheries Research*, 53 (3), 219-233
809

810 Chung, E.-Y., Hur, S.B., Hur, Y.-B., Lee, J.S., 2001. Gonadal maturation and artificial
811 spawning of the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Bivalvia: Veneridae), in Komso Bay,
812 Korea. *J. Fish. Sci. Tech.* 4, 208-218.
813

814 Dippner, J.W., 2004. Mathematical modelling of the transport of pollution in water, in
815 *Mathematical Models*, edited by J. A. Filar and J. B. Krawczyk in *Encyclopedia of Life Support*
816 *Systems (EOLSS)*, Developed under the Auspices of the UNESCO, Eolss Publishers,
817 Oxford,UK, [<http://www.eolss.net>].
818

819 Edwards, K. P., Hare, J.A., Werner, F.E., Seim, H., 2007. Using 2-dimensional dispersal
820 kernels to identify the dominant influences on larval dispersal on continental shelves. *Mar. Ecol.*
821 *Prog. Ser.* 352, 77–87.
822

823 Epifanio, C. E., Masse, A.K., Garvine, R.W., 1989. Transport of blue crab larvae by surface
824 currents off Delaware Bay, USA. *Mar. Ecol. Progr. Ser.* 54, 35-41.
825

826 Forward, R.B., 1987. Larval release in decapod crustaceans: an overview. *Bull Mar Sci* 41, 65-
827 176.
828

829 Gaines, S.D., Bertness, M., 1993. The dynamics of juvenile dispersal: why field ecologists must
830 integrate. *Ecology* 74, 2430-2435.
831

832 Galván, C., Juanes, J.A., Puente, A., 2010. Ecological classification of European transitional
833 waters in the North-East Atlantic eco-region. *Estuarine, coastal and shelf science* 87 (3), 442-
834 450.
835

836 García, A., Juanes, J.A., Álvarez, C., Revilla, J.A., Medina, R., 2010a. Assesment of the
837 response of a shallow macrotidal estuary to changes in hydrological and wastewater inputs
838 through numerical modelling. *Ecological Modelling* 221, 1194-1208.
839

840 García, A., Sámano, M.L., Juanes, J.A., Medina, R., Revilla, J.A., Álvarez, C., 2010b.
841 Assessment of the effects of a port expansion on algae appearance in a costal bay through
842 mathematical modelling. Application to San Lorenzo Bay (North Spain). *Ecological Modelling*
843 221, 1413–1426.
844

845 Gove D, Paula J., 2000. Rhythmicity of larval release in three species of intertidal brachyuran
846 crabs (Crustacea: Brachyura) from Inhaca Island (Mozambique). *Mar Biol* 136, 685-691.
847

848 Herbert, R. J. H., Willis, J., Jones, E., Ross, K., Hübner, R., Humphreys, J., Jensen, A., Baugh,
849 J., 2012. Invasion in tidal zones on complex coastlines: modelling larvae of the non-native
850 Manila clam, *Ruditapes philippinarum*, in the UK. *Journal of Biogeography* 39, 585-599.
851

852 Hinata, H., Tomisu, K., 2005. Numerical simulation on advective process of planktonic larvae
853 of the clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* in Tokyo Bay. *Bulletin Fisheries Research Agency*,
854 Supplement 3, 59–66.
855

856 Hinata, H., Furukawa, K., 2006. Ecological network linked by the planktonic larvae of the clam
857 *Ruditapes philippinarum* in Tokyo Bay, in: E. Wolanski (Ed), The environment in Asia Pacific
858 Harbours, Netherlands, pp. 35-45.
859

860 Hinckley, S., Hermann, A.J., Mier, K.L., Megrey, B.A., 2001. Importance of spawning location
861 and timing to successful transport to nursery areas: a simulation study of Gulf of Alaska walleye
862 pollock. ICES J Mar Sci 58, 1042–1052.
863

864 Hinrichsen, H.-H., Kraus, G., Böttcher, U., Köster, F., 2009. Identifying eastern Baltic cod
865 nursery grounds using hydrodynamic modelling: knowledge for the design of Marine Protected
866 Areas. ICES Journal of Marine Science: Journal du Conseil 66(1), 101-108.
867

868 Hirzel, A., 2001. When GIS comes to life. Linking landscape- and population ecology for large
869 population management modelling: the case of Ibex (*Capra ibex*) in Switzerland. PhD thesis.
870 Inst Ecol, Lab Conserv Biol. Univ Lausanne, Switzerland
871

872 Hirzel, A.H., Hausser, J., Chessel, D., Perrin, N., 2002. Ecological-niche factor analysis: how to
873 compute habitatsuitability maps without absence data? Ecology 83, 2027– 2036.
874

875 Hsieh, C-h., Reiss, C. S., Hunter, J. R., Beddington, J. R., May, R. M., Sugihara, G., 2006.
876 Fishing elevates variability in the abundance of exploited species. Nature 443, 859–862.
877

878 Hunt, H.L., Scheibling, R.E., 1997. Role of early post-settlement mortality in recruitment of
879 benthic marine invertebrates. Mar Ecol Prog Ser 155, 269–301
880

881 Hunter, J.R., 1987. The application of Lagrangian particle-tracking techniques to modelling of
882 dispersion in the sea. In: Noye, J. (Ed.), Numerical Modelling: Application to Marine Systems.
883 Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 257–269.
884

885 Incze, L. S., Naimie, C.E., 2000. Modeling the transport of lobster (*Homarus americanus*)
886 larvae and postlarvae in the Gulf of Maine. Fisheries Oceanography 9, 99-113.

887 Ishii, R., Sekiguchi, H., Nakahara, Y. & Jinnai, Y., 2001. Larval recruitment of the manila clam
888 *Ruditapes philippinarum* in Ariake Sound, southern Japan. Fisheries Science 67, 579– 591.

889 Ishii, R., Sekiguchi, H. & Jinnai, Y., 2005. Vertical distributions of larvae of the clam *Ruditapes*
890 *philippinarum* and the striped horse mussel *Musculista senhousia* in eastern Ariake Bay,
891 southern Japan. Journal of Oceanography 61, 973–978.

892 Jones, P.J.S., 2006. Collective action problems posed by no-take zones. Marine Policy 30, 143-
893 156.
894

895 Juanes, J.A., Bidegain, G., Echavarri-Erasun ,B., Puente, A., García, A., García, A., Bárcena, J.F.,
896 Álvarez, C., García-Castillo, G., 2012. Differential distribution pattern of native *Ruditapes*
897 *decussatus* and introduced *Ruditapes philippinarum* clam populations in the Bay of Santander
898 (Gulf of Biscay). Considerations for fisheries management, Ocean and Coastal Management 69,
899 316-326.
900

901 Kim, C.-K., Park, K. and Powers, S. P., 2012. Establishing Restoration Strategy of Eastern
902 Oyster via a Coupled Biophysical Transport Model. Restoration Ecology. doi: 10.1111/j.1526-
903 100X.2012.00897.x
904

905 Koutitas C., 1988. Mathematical models in Coastal Engineering. Pentech Press Limited,
906 London,UK.
907

908 Kowalik, Z., Murty, T., 1993. Numerical modeling of ocean dynamics. World Scientific
909 Publishing. Singapore, 481 pp.

910 Kuroda, N., 2005. Larval transportation and settlement mechanism to tidal flat in Japanese
911 littleneck clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*. Bulletin Fisheries Research Agency, Supplement 3,
912 S67–S77.

913 Laing I., Child A.R., 1996. Comparative tolerance of small juvenile palourdes (*Tapes*
914 *decussatus* L.) and Manila clams (*Tapes philippinarum* Adams & Reeve) to low temperature.
915 Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 195, 267 – 285.
916

917 Largier, J. L., 2003. Considerations in estimating larval dispersal distances from oceanographic
918 data. Ecological Applications 13 (1), S71–S89.
919

920 Lefebvre, A., Ellien, C., Davoult, D., Thiebaut, E., Salomon, J.C., 2003. Pelagic dispersal of the
921 brittle-star *Ophiothrix fragilis* larvae in a megatidal area (English Channel, France) examined
922 using an advection/ diffusion model. Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci. 57, 421–433.
923

924 Leis, J.M., 2006. Are larvae of demersal fishes plankton or nekton? Adv Mar Biol 51, 59–141.
925

926 Levitan, D.R., 1995. The ecology of fertilization in free-spawning invertebrates, In L.
927 McEdward (Ed), Ecology of marine invertebrate larvae. CRC Press. p. 123–156.
928

929 López, I., Álvarez, C., Gil, J.L., García, A., Bárcena, J.F., Revilla, J.A., 2013. A method for the
930 source apportionment in bathing waters through the modelling of wastewater discharges:
931 Development of an indicator and application to an urban beach in Santander (Northern Spain).
932 Ecological Indicators 24, 334-343.
933

934 Mann, R., 1986. *Arctica islandica* (Linne) larvae: active depth regulators or passive particles.
935 Am Mal. Union Spec. Ed. 3, 51-57.
936

937 Matias, D., Joaquim, S., Leitao, A., Massapina, C., 2009. Effect of geographic origin,
938 temperature and timing of broodstock collection on conditioning, spawning success and larval
939 viability of *Ruditapes decussates* (Linne, 1758). Aquacult. Int., 17, 257-271.
940

941 Metaxas, A., Saunders, M., 2009. Quantifying the “bio”- components in biophysical models of
942 larval transport in marine benthic invertebrates: Advances and pitfalls. Biological Bulletin 216,
943 257–272.
944

945 Minchinton, T.E., Scheibling, R.S., 1991. The influence of larval supply and settlement on the
946 population structure of barnacles. Ecology 72, 1867–1879.
947

948 Miyake, Y., Kimura, S., Kawamura, T., Horii, T., Kurogi, H., Kitagawa, T., 2009. Simulating
949 larval dispersal processes for abalone using a coupled particle-tracking and hydrodynamic
950 model: implications for refugium design. Mar Ecol Prog Ser 387:205-222
951

952 Morgan, S. G., 1995. Life and death in the plankton: larval mortality and adaptation, in:
953 Ecology of Marine Invertebrate Larvae, L. R. McEdward, ed. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, pp.
954 279–321.
955

956 Myers, R. A., 1997. Comment and reanalysis: paradigms for recruitment studies. *Can. J. Fish.*
957 *Aquat. Sci.*, 54: 978–981.

958

959

960 North, E.W., Schlag, Z., Hood, R.R., Zhong, L., Li, M., Gross, T., 2006. Modeling dispersal of
961 *Crassostrea ariakensis* oyster larvae in Chesapeake Bay. Maryland Department of Natural
962 Resources, 55 p.

963

964 North, E.W., Schlag, Z., Hood, R.R., Li, M., Zhong, L., Gross, T., Kennedy, V. S., 2008.
965 Vertical swimming behaviour influences the dispersal of simulated oyster larvae in a coupled
966 particle-tracking and hydrodynamic model of Chesapeake Bay. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 359, 99-
967 115.

968

969 North, E.W., Gallego, A., Petitgas, P., 2009. Manual of recommended practices for modelling
970 physical–biological interactions during fish early life. ICES Cooperative Research Report No.
971 295, International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), Copenhagen.

972

973 Ojea, J., Martínez, D., Novoa, S., Cerviño-Otero, A., 2005. Ciclo gametogénico de una
974 población de almeja japonesa *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve, 1850) en la ría de
975 Camariñas (noroeste de España) y relación con la composición bioquímica mayoritaria. *Boletín.*
976 *Instituto Español de Oceanografía* 21(1-4), 337-442.

977

978 Park, K.L., Choi, K.S., 2004. Application of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for studying
979 of reproduction in the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Mollusca: Bivalvia): I.
980 Quantifying eggs. *Aquaculture* 241 (1–4), 667-687.

981

982 Pérez-Camacho A. 1980. Biología de *Venerupis pullastra* (Montagu 1803) y *Venerupis*
983 *decussata* (Linne 1767) (Mollusca, Bivalvia), con especial referencia a los factores
984 determinantes de la producción. Bol. Inst. Esp. Oceanogr. 281, 44–74.
985
986 Perianez, R., 2004. A particle-tracking model for simulating pollutant dispersion in the Strait of
987 Gibraltar. Marine Pollution Bulletin 49 (7–8), 613–623.
988
989 Perianez, R., Elliott, A.J., 2002. A particle tracking method for simulation the dispersion of non-
990 conservative radionuclides in coastal waters. Journal of Environmental Radioactivity 58 (1),13–
991 33.
992
993 Peterson, C.H., 2002. Recruitment overfishing in a bivalve mollusc fishery: hard clams
994 (*Mercenaria mercenaria*) in North Carolina. Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science
995 59, 96-104
996
997 Pineda, J., Hare, J.A., Sponaugle, S., 2007. Larval dispersal and transport in the coastal ocean
998 and consequences for population connectivity. Oceanography 20, 22–39.
999
1000 Proctor, R., Elliott, A.J., Flather, R.A., 1994. Forecast and hindcast simulations of the Braer oil
1001 spill. Marine Pollution Bulletin 28 (4), 219–229.
1002
1003 Puente, A., Juanes, J.A., García-Castrillo, G., Álvarez, C., Revilla, J.A., Gil, J.L., 2002. Baseline
1004 study of soft bottom benthic assemblages in the bay of Santander (Gulf of Biscay).
1005 Hydrobiologia 475/476, 141–149.
1006

1007 Rigal, F., Viard, F., Ayata, S.D., Comtet, T., 2010. Does larval supply explain the low
1008 proliferation of the invasive gastropod *Crepidula fornicata* in a tidal estuary? *Biological*
1009 *Invasions* 12 , 3171-3186.
1010
1011 Rodriguez, S.R., Ojeda, F.P., Inestrosa, N.C., 1993. Settlement of benthic marine invertebrates.
1012 *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 97, 193–207.
1013
1014 Rodriguez-Moscoso, E., Pazo, J.P., Garcia, A., Cortés, F.F., 1992. Reproductive cycle of Manila
1015 clam, *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve 1850) in Ria of Vigo (NW Spain). *Scientia*
1016 *Marina* 56(1), 61-67.
1017
1018 Rodríguez-Moscoso, E., Arnaiz, R., 1998. Gametogenesis and energy storage in a population of
1019 the grooved carpet-shell clam, *Tapes decussatus* (Linné, 1787), in northwest Spain.
1020 *Aquaculture* 162(1-2), 125-139.
1021
1022 Roegner, G. C., 2000. Transport of larval molluscs through a shallow estuary. *Journal of*
1023 *Plankton Research* 22, 1779-1800
1024
1025 Roegner, G. C., Armstrong, D., Shanks, A., 2007. Wind and tidal influences on crab recruitment
1026 to an Oregon estuary. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 35, 177-188.
1027
1028 Roughan, M., Macdonald, H.S., Baird., M.E., Glasby, T.M., 2011. Modelling coastal
1029 connectivity in a Western Boundary Current: seasonal and inter- annual variability. *Deep-Sea*
1030 *Res. Part II* 58, 628–644.
1031
1032 Roughgarden, J., Gaines, S., Possingham, H.P., 1988. Recruitment dynamics in complex life
1033 cycles. *Science* 241, 1460–1466.

1032

1033 Savina, M., Lacroix, G., Ruddick, K., 2010. Modelling the transport of common sole larvae in
1034 the southern North Sea: Influence of hydrodynamics and larval vertical movements. J Mar Syst
1035 81, 86–98.

1036

1037 Siegel, D.A., Kinlan, B.P., Gaylord, B., Gaines, S.D., 2003. Lagrangian descriptions of marine
1038 larval dispersion. Marine Ecology Progress Series 260, 83-96.

1039

1040 Solidoro, C., Pastres, R., Melaku-Canu, D., Pellizzato, M., Rossi, R., 2000. Modelling the
1041 growth of *Tapes philippinarum* in Northern adriatic lagoons. Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 199, 137-
1042 148.

1043

1044 Spencer, B.E., Edwards, D.B., Millican, P.F., 1991. Cultivation of Manila clam. Lab. Leaflet,
1045 MAFF Direct. Fish. Res., Lowestoft, 29 pp.

1046

1047 Stephens, S.A., Broekhuizen, N., Macdiarmid, A.B., Lundquist, C.J., McLeodand, L., Haskew,
1048 R., 2006. Modelling transport of larval New Zealand abalone (*Haliotis iris*) along an open coast.
1049 Marine Freshwater Research 57, 519-532.

1050

1051 Suzuki, T., Ichikawa, T., Momoi, M., 2002. The Approach to Predict Sources of Pelagic
1052 Bivalve Larvae Supplied to Tidal Flat Areas by Receptor Mode Model: A Modeling Study
1053 Conducted in Mikawa Bay. Bulletin of the Japanese Society of Fisheries Oceanography 2, 88-
1054 101

1055

1056 Tamburri, M.N, Finelli, C.M, Wethey, D.S., Zimmer-Faust, R.K., 1996. Chemical induction of
1057 larval settlement behavior in flow. Biol Bull 191, 367–373

1058

1059 Thompson, C.M., 2011. Species-specific patterns in bivalve larval supply to a coastal
1060 embayment. Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute.
1061 PhD Thesis.
1062
1063 Tremblay, M.J., Loder, J.W., Werner, F.E., Naimie, C.E., Page, F.H., Sinclair M.M., 1994. Drift
1064 of sea scallop larvae *Placopecten magellanicus* on Georges Bank: a model study of the roles of
1065 mean advection, larval behavior and larval origin. Deep-Sea Res. Part II 47, 7–49.
1066
1067 Turner, E.J., Zimmer-Faust, R.K., Palmer, M.A., Luckenbach, M., Pentchef, N.D., 1994.
1068 Settlement of oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) larvae: effects of water flow and a water soluble
1069 chemical cue. Limnol Oceanogr 39, 1579–1593.
1070
1071 Urrutia, M.B., Ibarrola, I., Iglesias, J.I.P., Navarro, E., 1999. Energetics of growth and
1072 reproduction in a high-tidal population of the clam *Ruditapes decussatus* from Urdaibai Estuary
1073 (Basque Country, N. Spain). Journal of Sea Research 42(1), 35-48.
1074
1075 Vela, J.M., Moreno, O., 2005. Perfil bio-ecológico de la almeja fina (*Tapes decussatus* Linneo,
1076 1758), Acuicultura, Pesca y Marisqueo en el Golfo de Cádiz. Junta de Andalucía, pp. 641-662.
1077
1078 Verdier-Bonnet, C., Carlotti, F., Rey, C., Bhaud, M., 1997. A model of larval dispersal coupling
1079 wind-driven currents and vertical larval behaviour: application to the recruitment of the annelid
1080 *Owenia fusiformis* in Banyuls Bay, France. Mar Ecol Prog Ser 160, 217–231.
1081
1082 Vincenzi, S., Caramori, G., Rossi, R., Leo, G.A.D., 2006. A GIS-based habitat suitability model
1083 for commercial yield estimation of *Tapes philippinarum* in a Mediterranean coastal lagoon
1084 (Sacca di Goro, Italy). Ecological Modelling 193, (1-2), 90-104.
1085

1086 Yap, W.G., 1977. Population biology of the Japanese little-neck clam, *Tapes philippinarum*, in
1087 Kaneohe Bay, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands. *Pac Sci* 31(3), 223-244.
1088
1089 Ye, Y., 2000. Is recruitment related to spawning stock in penaeid shrimp fisheries – ICES
1090 *Journal of Marine Science* 57, 1103–1109.
1091
1092 Young-Baek, H., Jean-Hee, B., Sung-Bum, H., 2005. Comparison of Development and Larval
1093 Growth of Four Venerid Clams. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 36(2), 179-187.
1094
1095 Zhang, G., Yan, X., 2006. A new three-phase culture method for Manila clam, *Ruditapes*
1096 *philippinarum*, farming in northern China. *Aquaculture* 258, 452-461.
1097
1098 Zeng, C., Naylor, E., 1996. Endogenous tidal rhythms of vertical migration in field collected
1099 zoea-1 larvae of the shore crab *Carcinus maenas*: implications for ebb tide offshore dispersal.
1100 *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 132, 71– 82.

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1102

1103 **Figure footnotes**

1104

1105 **Figure 1** - Study area for the model: Bay of Santander estuary and adjacent waters located in
1106 the northern coast of Spain (Gulf of Biscay). Bathymetry (m) data of the modeled area are
1107 presented. Tidal-river annual mean currents (ms^{-1}) (a, b, c) and wind currents (d, e, f) for
1108 Spring, Summer and Autumn scenarios,

1109

1110

1111 **Figure 2** – Habitat suitability (HS) maps obtained from Bidegain et al. (2013) for *R.*
1112 *decussatus* (a) and *R. philippinarum* (b) in the Bay of Santander, classified into 4 HS index

1113 (HSI) classes using GIS techniques: unsuitable ($HSI < 25$), barely suitable ($25 \leq HSI < 50$),
1114 moderately suitable ($50 \leq HSI \leq 75$), highly suitable ($HSI > 75$). Spawning zones for *R.*
1115 *decussatus* (c) and *R. philippinarum* (d) considered in the simulations, delimited by areas with
1116 habitat suitability index values greater than 75 (i.e. highly suitable areas). Density of adult clams
1117 (> 20 mm) found by Bidegain et al. (2012) in each zone following the methodology of Juanes et
1118 al. (2012) is presented in brackets. A different color is given to each spawning ground which
1119 also represents the larvae coming from each of them in Figure 6.

1120

1121

1122 **Figure 3** – Observed (white quadrates) and predicted recruitment (individuals/m²) obtained with
1123 the LARVAHS model (black circles), the NO BEHAVIOR model (gray triangles) and the NO
1124 HS model (black crosses) are presented. Results are presented for Spring, Summer and Autumn
1125 season scenarios, for *R. decussatus* (A, B) and *R. philippinarum* (C, D) in Elechas and Raos
1126 sites respectively. Error bars for observed data represent the standard error.

1127

1128 **Figure 4** – *R. decussatus* larval dynamics regarding vertical behavior are represented in time
1129 sequential figures: (A) Day 1 (B) Day 5, (C) Day 15 and (D) Day 18. In right subfigures of each
1130 sequential figures points and lines represent the particle-tracking of two randomly selected
1131 larvae.

1132

1133

1134 **Figure 5** – Spatial representation of predicted recruitment for *R. decussatus* in Spring (a),
1135 Summer (b) and Autumn (c) scenarios and for *R. philippinarum* in the same scenarios
1136 respectively (d, e, f). Rectangles represent spawning zones and dots represent larvae recruited
1137 coming from their respective same color spawning zone. Colors used are identical to those
1138 given in Figure 2.

1139

1140 **Figure 6** – Connectivity matrices adapted from Savina et al. (2010) for the 3 seasonal scenarios
1141 (Spring, Summer and Autumn) and 2 tidal scenarios (neap and spring tides) simulated for *R.*
1142 *decussatus* (A) and *R. philippinarum* (B). The colors indicate the percentage of the total larvae
1143 recruited in a given nursery ground (x-axis) coming from each spawning ground (y-axis).

1144

1145 **Figure 7** –Success in recruitment of each spawning ground in terms of final recruitment within
1146 the whole Bay, presented by means of predicted final recruitment (%) in different seasonal
1147 scenarios (Spring, Summer and Autumn) for (a) *R. decussatus* and (b) *R. philippinarum*. The
1148 error bars represent the \pm SE of the mean recruitment of neap and spring tide scenarios.

1149

1150 **Figure 8** – Predicted recruitment density in nursery grounds (Habitat suitability index, HSI>75),
1151 calculated as the sum of recruitment of larvae coming from all spawning grounds at different
1152 seasons and tidal scenarios and divided by the total area of the nursery ground.

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Table 1

Life cycle	Life days <i>R. decussatus</i>	Life days <i>R. philippinarum</i>	Swimming capability	Direction and movement probability	Swimming speed (mm/s)
Egg	0 – 1	0 – 1	No	0	0
Trochophore Larvae	1 – 2	1 – 2	Yes	90% chance of move up	0.5
D, Umbo Larvae	2 – 14	2 – 10	Yes	Probabilities that shift their distribution from the upper layer to the lower layer as they increase in age, from a 51% chance of move up in each time step to a 51.7% chance of swimming down (linear function of particle age).	0.5-3 (speed increases linearly with age)
Pediveliger Larvae	15 – 21	10 – 15	Yes	100% chance of move down and stay within a 1 m water column from sea-bottom. In this water column, 50% chance of move up and 50% chance of move down	3

Table 1- Summary of larval behavior for *R. decussatus* and *R. philippinarum*. It details, for egg and larval phases, the duration (life days) and the capability and the vertical swimming behavior, adapted from Suzuki et al. (2002), Kuroda (2005), Ishii et al. (2005) and North et al. (2006:2008).

Table 2

Run	Season	Tide	Zone of release	Released (n)		Recruited LARVAHS (%)		Recruited NO BEHAVIOR (%)		Recruited NO HS (%)	
				<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R.phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R.phil.</i>	<i>R.dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>	<i>R. dec.</i>	<i>R. phil.</i>
1-37	Spring	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.036	0.144	0.009	0.027	0.461	1.027
2-38	Spring	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.009	0.011	0.001	0.002	0.282	0.639
3-39	Spring	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.062	0.036	0.019	0.000	0.690	0.804
4-40	Spring	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.215	0.460
5-41	Spring	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.005	0.015	0.006	0.030	0.191	0.628
6-42	Spring	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.004	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.234	0.384
43	Spring	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.808	–	0.410	–	1.587
7-44	Spring	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.014	0.089	0.007	0.051	0.337	0.818
8-45	Spring	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.203	0.353
9-46	Spring	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.030	0.006	0.008	0.000	0.439	0.722
10-47	Spring	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.115	0.242
11-48	Spring	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.056	0.297	0.018	0.390	0.187	0.717
12-49	Spring	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.011	0.052	0.009	0.035	0.200	0.524
50	Spring	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.676	–	0.290	–	1.514
13-51	Summer	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.222	0.687	0.029	0.350	1.480	1.623
14-52	Summer	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.034	0.200	0.026	0.230	0.994	1.225
15-53	Summer	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.089	0.064	0.021	0.074	1.219	1.319
16-54	Summer	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.024	0.051	0.021	0.220	0.914	0.909
17-55	Summer	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.015	0.536	0.766
18-56	Summer	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.009	0.052	0.013	0.080	0.722	0.908
57	Summer	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.115	–	0.360	–	1.718
19-58	Summer	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.084	0.260	0.070	0.210	0.973	1.202
20-59	Summer	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.011	0.021	0.022	0.097	0.898	0.920
21-60	Summer	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.121	0.032	0.038	0.068	1.393	1.231
22-61	Summer	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.013	0.016	0.020	0.070	0.934	0.890
23-62	Summer	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.020	0.015	0.002	0.019	0.964	0.951
24-63	Summer	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.052	0.002	0.052	0.951	0.978
64	Summer	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.006	–	0.090	–	1.746
25-65	Autumn	Neap	Astillero	187922	127912	0.104	0.447	0.013	0.260	0.934	1.256
26-66	Autumn	Neap	Elechas	75924	332893	0.016	0.041	0.007	0.290	0.352	0.589
27-67	Autumn	Neap	Raos	67704	50127	0.018	0.038	0.062	0.110	0.634	0.844
28-68	Autumn	Neap	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.308	0.643
29-69	Autumn	Neap	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.000	0.007	0.001	0.001	0.392	0.699
30-70	Autumn	Neap	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.013	0.035	0.009	0.068	0.378	0.681
71	Autumn	Neap	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	1.149	–	0.310	–	1.769
31-72	Autumn	Spring	Astillero	187922	127912	0.021	0.101	0.007	0.069	0.358	0.817
32-73	Autumn	Spring	Elechas	75924	332893	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.248	0.412
33-74	Autumn	Spring	Raos	67704	50127	0.038	0.040	0.010	0.002	0.809	0.790
34-75	Autumn	Spring	Pedreña	164052	963480	0.002	0.006	0.001	0.001	0.288	0.553
35-76	Autumn	Spring	Cubas O.	813750	26908	0.006	0.007	0.002	0.001	0.292	0.810
36-77	Autumn	Spring	Cubas I.	44485	5724	0.007	0.017	0.001	0.001	0.396	0.699
78	Autumn	Spring	Solía-T.	–	100812	–	0.824	–	0.190	–	1.722

Table 2 – Predicted recruitment scores (%) for simulated *R. decussatus* (*R. dec*) and *R. philippinarum* (*R. phil.*) eggs released (= released particles x 10⁵) from each spawning zone (Astillero, Elechas, Raos, Pedreña, Cubas Outer, Cubas Inner, Solía-Tijero) in each seasonal (spring, summer and autumn) and tidal amplitude (spring or neap tides) scenario, for a total of 36 runs for *R. decussatus* (1-36, left digit in column 1) and 42 for *R. philippinarum* (37-78, right digit in column 1). Results computed by (1) LARVAHS model, (2) LARVAHS model with no

behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and LARVAHS model with no habitat suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS) are presented.

Table 3

Species	Recruitment succes (%)			ANOVA test				
	LARVAHS	NO BEHAVIOR	NO HS	df	SS	MS	F	p
<i>R. decussatus</i>	0.03 ±0.01 A	0.01 ±0.002 B	0.58 ±0.06 C	2	75.8	37.9	122.3	***
<i>R. philippinarum</i>	0.20 ±0.05 A	0.11 ±0.02 B	0.93 ±0.06 C	2.0	70.0	35.0	37.7	***

Table 3 – Recruitment success (%; Mean ± SE) for *R. decussatus* (n= 36 simulations) and *R. philippinarum* (n=42) obtained using (i) the LARVAHS model, which incorporates larval behavior and habitat suitability based recruitment submodel, (ii) LARVAHS model with no behavior submodel (NO BEHAVIOR) and) (iii)LARVAHS model with no Habitat Suitability based recruitment submodel (NO HS). Results of the analysis of variance between recruitment obtained using different models are presented at right (*= p<0.05; **= p<0.001; ***= p <0.0001). Tukey HSD – test results are presented by letters (A, B, C) placed after each model mean. If any two means have at least one letter in common, they are not significantly different.

Table 4

Recruitment succes (%)						
<i>R. decussatus</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	—	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Season	2	1.814	13.5	0.907	4.97	0.002 *
Tide	1	0.033	2.4	0.033	0.07	0.80
Spawning zone	5	8.381	62.2	1.680	9.19	0.001 *
Season x Tide	2	0.001	0.01	0.001	0.001	1.00
Season x Spawning zone	10	0.016	0.1	0.002	1.76	0.14
Tide x Spawning zone	5	2.927	21.7	0.585	2.70	0.04 *
Total		13.17				

<i>R. philippinarum</i>						
Season	2	2.140	8.0	1.068	3.90	0.04 *
Tide	1	0.258	0.9	0.258	0.37	0.55
Spawning zone	6	19.26	71.9	3.209	21.84	0.0001 ***
Season x Tide	2	0.061	0.2	0.181	0.17	0.89
Season x Spawning zone	12	3.190	11.9	0.262	1.78	0.12
Tide x Spawning zone	6	1.879	7.0	0.313	1.69	0.16
Total		26.78				

Table 4 – Multifactorial analysis of variance observed in recruitment. Three explanatory variables are considered: Tide amplitude (at which the runs start: neap or spring tide) and Season (at which the run executes; spring, summer and autumn were the seasons considered, governed by different predominating winds) which account for different hydrodynamic conditions and the Spawning zone from where the particles or eggs are released. Df: degrees of freedom, the sum of squares (SS) and the mean sum of square (MS) are estimates of the variance attributed to the explanatory variable. The ratio between SS and SST (total sum of squares) x 100 represents the contribution in percentage of the each factor to the overall variance. F is the statistic of the analysis of variance and the p-value corresponds to the probability that there is no difference in means between the different levels of the explanatory variable, and therefore significant effects can be deduced from $p < 0.05$ highlighted by an asterisks (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.001$; *** = $p < 0.0001$).

Video S1

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